

Lightweight Rule-Based Host Intrusion Detection for Resource-Constrained Systems

Harry Derouich

Student ID: 2304874

BSc Computer Science

Department of Computing and Information Sciences

Anglia Ruskin University, Cambridge

24 April 2026

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor, Dr Segun Popoola, for their guidance throughout this project. I also thank my friends — Rafa, Mark, and Erik — for their encouragement, and my family for their support.

Consistent effort shapes the outcome.

Contents

1	Introduction	10
1.1	Background of the Study	10
1.2	Research Problem	10
1.3	Aim and Objectives	10
1.4	Methodology	11
1.5	Scope of the Study	11
1.6	Project Overview	11
1.7	Report Structure	11
2	Literature Review/Previous Work	12
2.1	Introduction & Background	12
2.1.1	Defining a Constrained System	12
2.1.2	HIDS vs. NIDS	13
2.1.3	Log-based Detection	13
2.1.4	IDS Implementation	14
2.1.5	Importance of Rule Design	14
2.2	Rule-Based & Signature Detection	14
2.2.1	Rule Construction	14
2.2.2	Advantages of Rule-based Detection	14
2.2.3	Disadvantages of Rule & Signature-based Detection	15
2.2.4	Current Relevance of Rule-based Detection	15
2.3	Host-Based Detection	15
2.3.1	Host Data Benefits	15
2.3.2	Host Data Challenges	16
2.4	Gap 1: Lightweight / Resource-Constrained Systems	16
2.4.1	Suitability of Current Solutions	16
2.4.2	Recent Trends	16
2.4.3	Relevancy and Gap	17
2.5	Gap 2: Air-Gapped / Isolated Environments	17
2.5.1	Threats to an Air-Gapped Network	17
2.5.2	Suitability of Current Solutions	17
2.5.3	Relevancy and Gap	17
2.6	Explainability/Transparency	17
2.6.1	Rule-based vs. Machine Learning Explainability	18
2.6.2	Offline Transparency	18
2.7	Recent Literature	18
2.8	Research Gap	19
2.9	Performance and Evaluation Context	19
3	Methodology	21
3.1	Research Approach	21
3.2	Detection Methodology	21
3.2.1	Rule-Based Detection Rationale	21
3.2.2	Rule Logic	21
3.2.3	Explainability vs. Machine Learning	21
3.3	Data Source	22

3.4	Dataset Generation	22
3.4.1	Manually Generated Data	22
3.4.2	Synthetically Generated Data	22
3.5	Tools and Technologies	23
3.5.1	Programming Language % Libraries	23
3.5.2	Data Technologies	23
3.5.3	Virtualisation	23
3.6	Limitations	23
4	System Design	24
4.1	System Architecture	24
4.1.1	Layer Breakdown	24
4.1.2	Modularity	24
4.2	Application Architecture	25
4.3	Database Design	26
4.3.1	Database 1: Relational	26
4.3.2	Database 2: Analytical	26
4.3.3	Database EERD	27
4.4	Rule Engine Design	27
4.4.1	Rule Types	28
4.4.2	Functionality	28
4.5	Data Flow	28
4.5.1	Upload, Parsing & Standardisation	28
4.5.2	Analysis & Results	28
4.6	User Interaction Planning	31
4.6.1	Purpose	31
4.6.2	Dashboard GUI	31
4.6.3	Processing GUI	32
4.6.4	Results GUI	32
4.6.5	Rule Management GUI	33
4.6.6	Use Case Diagram	34
5	Implementation and Results	35
5.1	Log Parsing	35
5.1.1	Regular Expression Matching	35
5.1.2	Parsing Considerations	35
5.2	Event Standardisation	35
5.2.1	Operations	35
5.3	Database Persistence	36
5.3.1	Hybrid Design Motivation	36
5.3.2	Coordinating the Hybrid Database	36
5.4	Rule Engine	36
5.4.1	Rule Features	36
5.4.2	Configuration Options	36
5.4.3	Alert Explainability & Drawbacks	37
5.5	Unit Testing and Validation	37
5.6	User Interface Implementation	37
5.6.1	Purpose & Technology Rationale	37

5.6.2	Initial Steps	38
5.6.3	Dashboard UI Implementation	38
5.6.4	Processing UI Implementation	39
5.6.5	Results UI Implementation	39
5.6.6	Rule Management UI Implementation	40
5.7	Challenges and Optimisation	41
5.7.1	Main Challenges	41
5.7.2	Parsing Challenges	41
5.7.3	Persistence Challenges	41
5.7.4	Minor Optimisations	41
5.8	Detection Evaluation	41
5.9	Detection Results	42
5.9.1	Generalised Detection Accuracy & Scalability	42
5.9.2	Event Parsing Accuracy	43
5.9.3	Malicious Activity Detection	44
5.10	Performance Evaluation	45
5.11	Performance Results	45
5.11.1	Test Conditions	45
5.11.2	Processing Time & CPU Usage	46
6	Discussion	47
6.1	System Performance	47
6.1.1	Linear Scalability	47
6.1.2	Resource Stability	47
6.2	Effectiveness of Rule-based Detection	48
6.2.1	Malicious Results Validation	48
6.2.2	Alert Evidence & Transparency	49
6.2.3	Benign Results Validation	49
6.2.4	Accuracy Validation & Critique	49
6.2.5	Assessing Rule Management	50
6.2.6	Reliability & Testing	50
6.3	Comparison with Machine Learning-based IDS	51
6.3.1	Benefits & Avoided Drawbacks	51
6.3.2	Restrictions vs. ML	51
6.4	Suitability for Constrained Environments	51
6.4.1	Self Containment	51
6.4.2	Performance-aware Functionality	51
6.5	Limitations	51
6.5.1	Scope of Detection Capabilities	51
6.5.2	Rule Limitations	52
6.5.3	Full Accuracy Evaluation	52
6.5.4	Reliance on Synthetic Datasets	52
6.5.5	On-demand Scanning	52
6.5.6	Testing Limitations	52
6.6	Evaluation Against Aims	53
7	Conclusion	54
7.1	Achievement of Aims	54

7.2	Key Contributions	54
7.3	Lessons Learned	54
7.4	Future Work	55
A	Experimental Setup and Environment	60
A.1	Hardware Specifications	60
A.2	Software Specifications	60
A.3	Test Conditions	60
A.4	Dataset Composition Summary	61
B	Rule Configuration	62
C	Example auth.log File	63
D	Database Schema	64
D.1	Scans: data/app.db (SQLite)	64
D.2	Events: data/scans/<scan_id>.duckdb (DuckDB)	64
D.3	Rules: data/app.db (SQLite)	64
E	Raw Data	65
E.1	Performance Timing	65
E.1.1	Baseline	65
E.1.2	Brute Force	66
E.2	Alert Outputs	67
E.3	Event Detection Accuracy	68
F	User Guide and Documentation	69
F.1	Installation & Getting Started	69
F.1.1	Prerequisites	69
F.1.2	Setup	69
F.2	User Guide	69
F.2.1	Dashboard	69
F.2.2	Processing	71
F.2.3	Results	72
F.2.4	Rules	74
F.3	Running Tests	76
F.4	Generating Logs	77
F.5	Troubleshooting / FAQs	77
G	Unit Testing	79

List of Figures

1	Illustration of modern device interconnectivity (PC Kings 2020)	12
2	Representation of an air-gapped network (Speculos 2023)	13
3	Component Diagram for the HIDS Application	24
4	Application Flow Diagram	25
5	Enhanced Entity-Relationship Diagram (EERD) for the HIDS Application	27
6	Data pipeline diagram showing how a .log file is analysed	28
7	Sequence Diagram for the HIDS Application	30
8	Dashboard Wireframe	31
9	Processing Page Wireframe	32
10	Results Page Wireframe	32
11	Rule Management Page Wireframe	33
12	Use Case Diagram for the HIDS Application	34
13	Implementation of the Dashboard using Streamlit	38
14	A new file being uploaded from the Dashboard	38
15	Implementation of the Processing page, showing a successfully processed file	39
16	Implementation of the Results page alerting	39
17	Two of the available six activity visualisations on the Results page	40
18	Implementation of the Rule Management system using Streamlit	40
19	Graph of processing time and CPU usage for baseline and bruteforce logs (100k to 1M rows)	47
20	Screenshot of the HIDS application showing successful detection of threats	48
21	Screenshot of the HIDS application showing evidence for the triggered alerts for bruteforce_100k.log	49
22	Screenshot of the HIDS application showing zero triggered alerts for baseline_100k.log	49
23	Screenshots of the HIDS application's rule management system	50
24	Annotated screenshot of viewing past scans from the dashboard	70
25	Annotated screenshot uploading a new log file from the dashboard	70
26	Annotated screenshot of uploading a file being successfully processed	71
27	Annotated screenshot of scan results showing alerts and event breakdown	72
28	Annotated screenshot of scan results showing alert breakdown and data visualisations	73
29	Annotated screenshot of scan results showing summary statistics and raw data views	73
30	Annotated screenshot of rules being viewed and edited	74
31	Annotated screenshot of a new rule being created	74
32	Annotated screenshot of new rule information being added	76

List of Tables

1	Summary of recent research on intrusion detection systems	19
2	Alert Summary of baseline and brute force files (100k-1M rows)	42
3	Detected Events bruteforce_100k	43
4	Detected Events bruteforce_250k	43
5	Detected Events bruteforce_500k	43
6	Detected Events bruteforce_1m	43
7	Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_100k	44
8	Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_250k	44
9	Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_500k	44
10	Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_1m	44
11	Testing data for 100,000 to 1,000,000 row log files	46
12	Event Summary	61
13	Alert Summary	61
14	Baseline - 100k	65
15	Baseline - 250k	65
16	Baseline - 500k	65
17	Baseline - 1M	65
18	Bruteforce - 100k	66
19	Bruteforce - 250k	66
20	Bruteforce - 500k	66
21	Bruteforce - 1M	66
22	Detected authentication-related alerts	67
23	Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_100k.log	68
24	Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_250k.log	68
25	Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_500k.log	68
26	Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_1m.log	68

Abstract

Intrusion detection systems (IDS) are core to modern cybersecurity. Today, machine-learning approaches to intrusion detection dominate the field. However, computational and connectivity requirements create a mismatch for their use within resource-constrained or isolated environments. Consequently, there is an absence of lightweight, self-contained solutions.

This project's aim is to design, implement, and evaluate a lightweight, host intrusion detection system, using a rule-based approach to threat detection in Linux authentication logs.

Key objectives are high performance on consumer-grade hardware, deterministic output, fully offline capabilities, and interpretable results.

The system demonstrates near-linear scaling of logs up to 1-million rows in length, successfully detecting attacks using its rule-based logic approach. Achieved deviation from ground truth is consistently within 0.02% deviation for malicious `login_fail` and `invalid_user` events.

Drawbacks of a rule-based approach limit the system to detection of known attack patterns, rather than unseen and novel attacks. The project successfully demonstrates the effectiveness of a lightweight HIDS, proving suitability for the target constrained environments set out in the stated objectives.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

The annual cost of cybercrime was over \$8 trillion globally in 2023, which is expected to grow to almost \$14 trillion by 2028 (Statista 2022). Worldwide, there are an estimated 2,200 cyberattacks daily, or one every 39 seconds (DeepStrike 2024). This can have severe business impact, with the average breach costing companies upwards of \$4 million (IBM 2023) and taking over 90 days to remedy (Verizon 2025). In particular, 61% of SMBs experienced a cyberattack in 2023 (BlackFog 2023), highlighting small organisations are commonly targeted. Specifically, over 80% of breaches involved brute forcing or credential abuse (Verizon Business 2023), showing the prevalence of authentication-based attacks.

Intrusion detection is a fundamental part of modern network security, aiming to identify malicious activity within a system or systems. Real-world networking environments can become complex, which paired with sophisticated attack techniques, make effective activity monitoring crucial. A Host-based Intrusion Detection System (HIDS) allows for system-level events to be explored, such as login and user behaviour. System logs, like `auth.log` on Linux, provide a readily available data source for analysis, without additional logging overhead.

1.2 Research Problem

Research into modern threat detection techniques focusses heavily on machine-learning approaches, which are disadvantageous due to requirements for large training datasets, considerable computational power, and frequent retraining. This limits usability in environments such as resource-constrained or isolated systems. Additionally, some machine-learning-based systems offer little transparency or interpretability of their results, lowering trust.

This project was motivated behind systems in the real-world having to operate under a constraint, such as limited CPU power, RAM, or lack of internet connectivity. This makes many popular enterprise-grade solutions unsuitable due to their reliance on these factors. This identifies a gap for a lightweight, explainable IDS, designed to operate in constrained environments.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The project's aim is to build a lightweight rule-based host intrusion detection system capable of analysing host logs efficiently within resource-constrained or offline environments.

Objectives:

1. Literature Review: Analyse existing research on host-based and rule-based intrusion detection, identifying limitations in efficiency, scalability, and deployment within constrained or offline contexts.
2. System Design: Plan a modular architecture for a lightweight, configurable rule-based log analysis system informed by findings from the literature.
3. Implementation: Develop the host intrusion detection prototype, integrating log parsing, rule evaluation, and alert generation.
4. Evaluation: Test the prototype's functionality and performance using sample log data to determine its suitability for lightweight or offline operation.

1.4 Methodology

The proposed approach is to begin with a comprehensive literature review covering previous work of this topic.

This will continue with the designing of a lightweight, rule-based HIDS. Key requirements are low computational overhead and functionality as a self-contained system without external dependencies. Simultaneously, its results must be transparent, allowing for explainable detection logic.

Structured log analysis will allow for identification of common attack patterns. The system aims to implement a deterministic rule-based approach to its detection logic, rather than relying on an opaque machine-learning model.

To evaluate its performance, many aspects of the system will be closely examined. These include raw performance and scalability, as well as threat detection effectiveness. By evaluating these metrics, the suitability of the system in the targeted constrained environments will be assessed. The expected results are accurate and deterministic analysis of datasets of an increasing size, delivering this performance without reliance on enterprise hardware or machine-learning.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This project aims to focus purely on host-based detection, using Linux authentication logs, and applying rule-based threat logic. It does not include network-wide or real-time detection, or employ the use of a purely machine-learning, or hybrid, model. Emphasis is placed on performance and suitability for constrained environments, over maximising threat detection depth.

1.6 Project Overview

This project sets out to provide a modern exploration of research on rule-based intrusion detection, within the current ML-dominated landscape. By developing a standalone intrusion detection prototype, the feasibility of this type of system can be demonstrated.

1.7 Report Structure

This report will begin with a literature review covering existing work on IDS threat detection and identifying a research gap. The methodology will be covered and the prototype's design will be justified. This is followed by an overview of the system's design and architecture, and how this was implemented. The report then reaches its evaluation, and concludes with a summary of the project's findings.

Figure 2: Representation of an air-gapped network (Speculos 2023)

An air-gapped system is defined as a computing environment physically isolated from external networks and the internet, preventing external system interconnectivity (National Institute of Standards and Technology 2015). This common as a security measure, limiting potential attack surface by preventing external network access.

These environments restrict the use of solutions that rely on continuous internet connectivity for telemetry, updates, or threat intelligence (Sommer and Paxson 2010). As a result, solutions designed for these environments must be able to operate independently, without reliance on external infrastructure.

2.1.2 HIDS vs. NIDS

An intrusion detection system (IDS) is a type of cybersecurity mechanism used to detect external or internal attacks against a confidential network system (Axelsson 2000). The two types of IDS are host-based intrusion detection systems (HIDS) and network intrusion detection systems (NIDS). The former focusses on monitoring a single host device for malicious activity, and the latter across a network, scanning for intrusions across traffic. A HIDS has the benefit of being able to detect other types of misuse, such as insider threats, with NIDS offering broader protection, at the expense of detail. Both can be used together for comprehensive internal and external protection (Bridges et al. 2019).

2.1.3 Log-based Detection

A HIDS can use various forms of data to detect threats (Bridges et al. 2019). Commonly, logs generated by applications and operating systems provide data for threat identification, including authentication, audit, system and service logs (Center for Internet Security 2019). Authentication logs provide a high-signal source of data to detect access-based attacks. These logs contain normal and malicious events, and the HIDS categorises them (Bergner and Landes 2025). By using automatically generated logs, additional data generation and collection overheads can be avoided. This supports authentication logs as an appropriate data source for intrusion detection within this project.

Detecting malicious activity through application logs involves interpreting multiple events because in isolation, single events are rarely a strong enough indicator. By looking at patterns that multiple events create, detection algorithm accuracy can be improved. By correlating single rows into sequences, patterns such as multiple login failures, followed by a success, can be detected (Abad et al. 2003). One way this can be achieved is by using rule-based logical tests, establishing a foundation for identifying suspicious authentication event patterns.

2.1.4 IDS Implementation

Standalone HIDSs can be developed using high-level programming languages, such as Python or Java (Wahal et al. 2018). At its core, pairing log parsing with a rule-based logic system allows for detection of common attacks. This demonstrates the feasibility of HIDSs and supports the practicality of these systems being developed (Jiang et al. 2026).

2.1.5 Importance of Rule Design

Rule-based intrusion detection systems have demonstrated effective network-based threat detection capabilities (Roesch 1999). However, the overall effectiveness is dependent on the design and structure of the rules (Parameshwarappa et al. 2018).

2.2 Rule-Based & Signature Detection

The detection system of a HIDS uses one of two approaches. This is either the rules being tested for defined logical conditions, or matching events to predefined attack patterns or sequences, known as signatures (Axelsson 2000). Signatures encode attacks which potential malicious events can be compared to. Detection logic can be applied to single events, such as a single unfamiliar login location, or a series of events (i.e. 5 failed logins from the same IP). This approach is used in some early and widely used IDSs (Roesch 1999), demonstrating this approach's practicality. Signatures allow for fast matching of attacks, making them foundational to many modern IDSs (Axelsson 2000).

2.2.1 Rule Construction

Detection rules are written using human-readable conditions like thresholds, patterns, or time spans (Parameshwarappa et al. 2018). When a rule is matched, it's classified and triggers an alert. The rule system is managed separately from system's source code (Roesch 1999), allowing for independent updates over time. A practical implementation separates the three main stages; data collection, rule evaluation, and alerts/logging (Bridges et al. 2019).

2.2.2 Advantages of Rule-based Detection

Rule-based detection has many advantages, such as predictable and deterministic behaviour (Axelsson 2000). Contrasting machine-learning-based systems, there is lower computational overhead and no training data requirement (Siwach and Mann 2022). This makes it suitable for resource-constrained or specialised systems (Ioulianou et al. 2018). The logic also offers transparency (Parameshwarappa et al. 2018), allowing for the system's outcome to be explainable and traced back to the events that triggered it.

2.2.3 Disadvantages of Rule & Signature-based Detection

Rule and signature-based IDSs do have drawbacks, such as reliance on prior knowledge of attack patterns to develop their rules (Axelsson 2000). This makes them vulnerable to zero-day attacks (Siwach and Mann 2022), allowing for attackers to implement simple modifications to evade fragile rules. This creates a trade-off between system adaptability and results interpretability. Over time, maintenance of the rule set can become cumbersome (Parameshwarappa et al. 2018), and the system utilising more rules can introduce processing overhead. Without continued maintenance over time, the detection system can lose effectiveness (Bridges et al. 2019).

2.2.4 Current Relevance of Rule-based Detection

Despite limitations, rule-based detection remains practical for certain scenarios. In practice, granular control and predictability are valuable, with some machine-learning approaches introducing undesirable opacity (Siwach and Mann 2022) and data requirements. Consequently, in resource-constrained or offline environments, rule-based systems can offer practicality over other system types. This contributes to their current use, either standalone or with another detection type like machine learning. This aligns with the design aims of this project, where low computation overhead and results transparency is prioritised, over detection of evolving threats.

To summarise, rule-based detection is underpinned by accurate data interpretation. The effectiveness of detection efforts is influenced by the source data and rule complexity (Bergner and Landes 2025). Opportunities for threat detection are presented by employing a rule-based system on host-generated logs (Jiang et al. 2026).

2.3 Host-Based Detection

Detection systems operating on a host perform scans against telemetry generated within the host's operating system (Bridges et al. 2019). Events are created during operations such as authentication attempts, privilege escalation, and audit processes (Jiang et al. 2026). Audit logs provide a routine, structured set of events that records the host's state in detail (Center for Internet Security 2019). Overall, host data provides an overview of the system's state and user interaction with it, identifying behavioural misuse at the source (Bridges et al. 2019).

2.3.1 Host Data Benefits

Examining host-level data can unveil behaviour that would be undetectable at the network level (Bridges et al. 2019). This includes privilege escalation, file tampering, and malicious activity occurring within the system (Jiang et al. 2026). Host-level visibility can be combined with network-based detection to offer comprehensive detection (Haas et al. 2020), and examining a series of events can allow for progression tracking of sophisticated attacks. Detailed event logs captured at host-level can offer richer semantic meaning than raw packets at network level (Jansen et al. 2024).

An ongoing attack can be tracked by investigating the sequence of system-level events that occur. Correlating different event types (e.g. authentication, process, network) strengthens detection algorithms (Abad et al. 2003). Each event is timestamped, improving the context over events in isolation (Bergner and Landes 2025). Correlation also allows for behavioural patterns to be identified by examining event relationships over time. The structured nature of host data is what allows for rule-based logic to function effectively (Jiang et al. 2026).

2.3.2 Host Data Challenges

Host-based detection introduces challenges to be considered. Log formats differ between operating systems and applications (Bergner and Landes 2025). Depending on event frequency and the log's time span, detection systems can become bottlenecked, performance-wise (Siwach and Mann 2022). Noise and false positives are a common occurrence when high data volumes are being examined (Axelsson 2000), as resource constraints can make deeper inspections problematic. Efficient processing is therefore crucial for real-time detection (Bridges et al. 2019).

An IDS is required to process large amounts of data efficiently (Bridges et al. 2019), so resource usage and deployment practicality need to be considered. Real-time detection and alerting introduces CPU and memory overhead for effective system function (Siwach and Mann 2022). Additionally, logging requirements introduce further processing overhead. This may involve balancing granularity and depth with performance (Bergner and Landes 2025). The most heavily iterated task is the rule scanning engine, with efficiency forming the foundation of its processing logic. With one intended environment being lightweight systems, this architecture mandates high resource awareness (Ioulianou et al. 2018).

To conclude, host-based detection system allows for in-depth process visibility at the cost of processing challenges. For an effective system, high-volume data must be managed without sacrificing accuracy (Bridges et al. 2019). The efficiency of HIDSs is pivotal due to their use in resource-constrained systems (Ioulianou et al. 2018).

2.4 Gap 1: Lightweight / Resource-Constrained Systems

The landscape of computer systems in use globally is broad, with many environments operating under a hardware constraint. Resources such as CPU power, memory, and storage capacity, can be limited (Pandey et al. 2025). Examples of particularly low-powered systems include embedded systems, consumer-grade hardware, and industrial control devices (Raza et al. 2013). In these environments, opting for enterprise-grade security solutions is not always possible due to computational overheads (Pandey et al. 2025), for which these systems are under-equipped.

2.4.1 Suitability of Current Solutions

Many traditional intrusion detection systems use resource-intensive operations (Bridges et al. 2019) like large rule sets and machine learning (Siwach and Mann 2022). This is because they are generally intended for enterprise environments, which typically have powerful hardware that can be allocated (Bridges et al. 2019), whereas consumer hardware usually has more resource scarcity.

2.4.2 Recent Trends

Recently, security solutions have gravitated towards using machine learning (Siwach and Mann 2022) to analyse large datasets and identify malicious behaviour. Their power is also their detriment, as considerable processing power is mandatory (Javaid et al. 2016). Even with recent advancements in machine learning, such as pruning and quantisation, the underlying resource requirement still exists (Pandey et al. 2025).

2.4.3 Relevancy and Gap

Whilst many modern detection approaches focus on machine learning (Siwach and Mann 2022) this introduces computational requirements. As a result, lightweight analysis techniques still have relevancy for use on low-powered systems. Rather than using machine learning for threat identification, simpler rule-based approaches can achieve this with lower computational overheads (Ioulianou et al. 2018). Despite this need, modern research focuses on machine learning and artificial intelligence (Siwach and Mann 2022), leaving a gap for a focussed study of intrusion detection for lightweight and constrained environments (Bridges et al. 2019). This project seeks to address this gap by developing a rule-based HIDS to analyse authentication activity with minimal overhead and high logic transparency.

2.5 Gap 2: Air-Gapped / Isolated Environments

Another type of constrained environment is an air-gapped environment that has been intentionally isolated from the internet to reduce security risks exposure. This is common in sectors such as research environments, nuclear control systems, and anywhere handling exceptionally sensitive data, such as government facilities. These environments isolate themselves from the internet to limit the attack surface (Zhu et al. 2011).

2.5.1 Threats to an Air-Gapped Network

Security measures designed towards external attacks still leave insider threats at risk of being exploited (Bridges et al. 2019; Greitzer and Frincke 2010). Host-based intrusion detection systems are still relevant to analyse logs, detecting whether this type of activity has occurred (Bridges et al. 2019).

2.5.2 Suitability of Current Solutions

Many modern solutions rely on internet connectivity for alerting, updating threat profiles (Siwach and Mann 2022), or connecting to distributed monitoring infrastructure (Bridges et al. 2019). This conflicts with air-gapped systems' lack of internet connectivity. Relating this to machine learning solutions, they require retraining and updated datasets to maintain novel and zero-day attack accuracy (Buczak and Guven 2015), presenting another deployment challenge. This limits their suitability within air-gapped environments.

2.5.3 Relevancy and Gap

Detection methods without connectivity reliance offer advantages in air-gapped environments. This highlights a gap for standalone intrusion detection systems with offline operation, which this project addresses by developing a self-contained detection system without any external dependencies.

2.6 Explainability/Transparency

The accuracy of an IDS is only part of its role. Being able to interpret scan results is important (Sommer and Paxson 2010), so analysts can understand what is happening and when. This requirement has led to interest in detection method explainability (Samek et al. 2017).

2.6.1 Rule-based vs. Machine Learning Explainability

The nature of machine-learning detection techniques mean that the results do not always clearly show an alert’s cause (Molnar et al. 2020). This can impede incident response (Sommer and Paxson 2010), with the lack of transparency limiting investigation into the cause.

A rule-based system works by triggering an alert when conditions are met (Axelsson 2000), making it easier to indicate what was matched. This allows for alerts to be evidenced with the triggering events (Parameshwarappa et al. 2018). During incident response, analysts can use this evidence to verify detection accuracy and determine whether an attack or false positive has occurred (Bridges et al. 2019).

2.6.2 Offline Transparency

Transparency is important in air-gapped environments as analysts cannot benefit from external threat intelligence, instead relying on locally available resources. This influenced the need for alerts in this project to be associated with the rule that was triggered and causal evidence shown.

2.7 Recent Literature

The table below contains a selection of recent IDS literature published within the last three years. This was collected to identify dominant trends and to what extent host-based detection, rule-based approaches, resource-constrained designs, and offline capabilities, are addressed.

For each study, the system type (HIDS/NIDS) and detection approach used is listed. "Constrained" indicates whether limited resources were explicitly considered, and offline denotes functionality without an internet connection. "Partially" constrained indicates that performance was indirectly considered in the study, rather than explicit resource-constrained design.

Study	Type	Approach	Constrained	Offline
A real-time deep learning based approach for detecting network attacks (Callegari et al. 2024)	NIDS	Deep Learning	No	No
A sequential deep learning framework for a robust and resilient network intrusion detection system (Hore et al. 2024)	NIDS	Deep Learning	No	No
Design and implementation of a deep neural network approach for intrusion detection systems (Osa et al. 2024)	NIDS	Deep Learning	No	No
Network security intrusion detection system based on deep learning (Fang and Leng 2025)	NIDS	Deep Learning	No	No
IDS-GPT: A novel deep learning-powered framework for network traffic intrusion detection (Saidi 2025)	NIDS	Deep Learning	No	No

Continued on next page

Study	Type	Approach	Constrained	Offline
A stacked machine learning-based intrusion detection system for smart connected vehicles (Zhou et al. 2025)	Hybrid	Machine Learning	Partial	No
An efficient machine learning-based network intrusion detection system (Sinha et al. 2023)	NIDS	Machine Learning	No	No
Hybrid deep learning model for network intrusion detection using optimal feature fusion (Harish et al. 2026)	NIDS	Hybrid ML	No	No

Table 1: Summary of recent research on intrusion detection systems

Table 1 shows that the majority of recent studies are on machine learning approaches, with many specifically using deep learning. No sampled papers used a non-machine-learning approach.

Additionally, host-based detection is not represented, and constrained environments are only indirectly considered in one study. No systems were designed for offline functionality.

These observations highlight that current research assumes the availability of computational power and connectivity. This reveals a gap for lightweight and offline-capable HIDSs, which this project aims to address.

2.8 Research Gap

Modern research focuses on breakthroughs in machine-learning approaches to increase detection accuracy. They benefit from processing large datasets and thoroughly analysing the events that have occurred (Buczak and Guven 2015).

Whilst these methods excel in well-equipped environments, they mandate increased hardware requirements, and add setup and maintenance complexity (Sommer and Paxson 2010). Section 2.7 shows recent IDS research is dominated by machine learning for threat detection, with minimal attention towards simpler approaches. This creates scope for lightweight intrusion detection systems to be explored within a modern context.

Section 2.7 also shows limited attention towards resource-constrained environments, and no consideration towards offline operation within the sampled studies. This project addresses this gap by designing and implementing a self-contained HIDS that can detect malicious activity with minimal computational overheads and transparent logic. The performance and detection capabilities of the developed system can be evaluated, allowing this project to prove the feasibility of this approach, offering standalone or complementary detection to machine-learning solutions. This approach provides simplicity, performance, and explainability, allowing for a practical alternative to machine-learning-based systems for constrained environments to be developed.

2.9 Performance and Evaluation Context

There are two areas to evaluate for an IDS (García-Teodoro et al. 2009). The first is accuracy detection, representing the ability to establish when malicious activity has occurred (Lippmann

et al. 2000). The second is system performance, relating to metrics like processing time and resource usage (García-Teodoro et al. 2009).

A HIDS that uses system resources unnecessarily may impede the use of the system it's supposed to protect (Bridges et al. 2019). Consequently, many studies already examine the scalability when processing larger amounts of data (García-Teodoro et al. 2009). Part of a system's effectiveness in real-world environments is its ability to cope with increasing volumes of log data (Bergner and Landes 2025).

Hosts with long system uptime or high activity will naturally result in the generation of larger logs. It's therefore key to analyse how the total processing time changes with larger datasets.

Evaluating these results establishes if a self-contained and lightweight approach can return accurate readings whilst scaling proportionally, demonstrating efficiency without machine learning or connected infrastructure.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

An artefact-based methodology was adopted, inline with the primary objective of developing a functional cybersecurity tool, rather than theoretical analysis. This is a common approach when the goal is to create a technical solution (Hevner et al. 2004) and allowed for controlled experimentation of the prototype's performance and detection capabilities. Being able to measure computational efficiency is crucial for evaluating system suitability in low-powered or constrained environments. The research conducted focussed on the workings of a prototype HIDS which can detect malicious activity from a log file.

Design choices for this prototype include high performance, results transparency, and a focus on simplicity over utilising complex machine-learning technologies. This was influenced by the targeted use environment; low-powered systems (resource-constrained) and systems in offline environments (air-gapped).

Prototype performance is assessed using programmatically timed controlled experiments, with baseline and malicious host logs as datasets. This allows for observation of system performance against regular and attack scenarios.

The key metrics to be measured can be broken down into two parts. Performance metrics, including processing time and CPU utilisation, indicate scalability potential of the system. Detection metrics evaluate the system's differentiation between benign and malicious data at aggregate level.

3.2 Detection Methodology

3.2.1 Rule-Based Detection Rationale

This project opts for a rule-based detection approach, which applies configurable rules to the selected file, identifying suspicious activity patterns (Roesch 1999). This was selected over machine learning for its deterministic behaviour, low computational overhead and lack of reliance on training data. This aligns with deployment requirements in constrained and air-gapped environments, where resources such as CPU power and internet connectivity are limited.

3.2.2 Rule Logic

The rules themselves mirror common behavioural patterns found in authentication logs, such as incorrect password attempts or the specified user not being found. An example attack type would be a brute force, with the corresponding rule looking for multiple failed login attempts from the same origin, within a specified time span. A match against this rule would trigger an alert that a brute force attack may have occurred.

3.2.3 Explainability vs. Machine Learning

Rule-based systems offer excellent explainability, evidencing what caused the alert. This method contrasts machine-learning models, which can offer less transparency on what caused events to be flagged. This makes the chosen approach more suitable when interpretability is desirable.

However, rule-based approaches prioritise explainability over adaptability against unseen or novel attack patterns.

3.3 Data Source

The artefact was designed for Linux authentication logs (`auth.log`). These are generated as standard on Linux installations (Bridges et al. 2019) and include user authentication events. `auth.log` was chosen as an automatically generated, structured data format, providing a readily available data source that doesn't require further development of a logging system, avoiding implementation overhead. This allows for raw events to be extracted and have rule-based logic applied to them, without any additional instrumentation. `auth.log` contains timestamped lines with origin IP addresses, usernames, and the outcomes of authentication attempts.

During log ingestion the system filters, processes, and extracts events relevant to authentication, such as failed and successful login attempts, and attempts to access invalid accounts. These event types allow for detection of brute force and enumeration attacks, using typical patterns.

3.4 Dataset Generation

3.4.1 Manually Generated Data

The first source of test data involved manual simulation of SSH authentication using two virtual machines. The 'victim' was a Ubuntu server installation and the 'attacker' was a Kali installation. Scenarios were launched from the attacker VM, using tools such as Hydra, which performs rapid automated username and password guessing, simulating a brute force attack. Manual login behaviour was also simulated to generate baseline activity, allowing for comparison between normal and malicious behaviour. This was automatically stored in `auth.log` and extracted between scenarios.

3.4.2 Synthetically Generated Data

To test performance at higher data volumes, synthetic datasets were used as a controlled data source. A custom generation script created longer logs with more variability (e.g. source IPs) than would be practical to run manually. This allowed for generation of logs with known characteristics and specific attack patterns, providing a basis for consistent testing across files of increasing size. This was important to assess the potential real-world performance of the system, allowing performance to be tested up to 1-million rows, which was infeasible to generate manually. Whilst synthetic logs were able to satisfy this size requirement, they cannot represent the variety found in real-world logs.

In addition to the `.log` file, the synthetic data generation script also produces a CSV representing the ground truth for each event, indicating whether it had malicious or benign origin. This allows for initial event labelling. However, subsequent alert abstraction prevents direct event-level evaluation. Additionally, a JSON file containing the attacks that were launched, each containing multiple events and whether it led to successful login, helps track scenarios used in the log. Malicious and benign events are intentionally launched from a shared range of IP addresses, with potential overlap mimicking the realism of a genuine attack.

3.5 Tools and Technologies

3.5.1 Programming Language & Libraries

As the core of the system is data and analysis, the Python programming language (v3.12) was chosen thanks to its strong ecosystem for data processing libraries (e.g. Pandas). Additionally, as a high-level software language, it offers rapid development capabilities for an analytical system of this type. Efficient, structured data processing aligns with the objective for lightweight system design.

Similarly, Streamlit (v1.54.0) was chosen as the GUI library due to its suitability for data visualisation. Streamlit enables rapid development of a UI without a separate frontend framework, allowing the system to operate with a single technology stack. This reduces overall system complexity, removing potential overhead dependency.

3.5.2 Data Technologies

A combination of SQLite (v3.50.4) and DuckDB (v1.4.4) databases are used. DuckDB offers excellent scalability for large data volumes, allowing for analytics to be quickly performed without external infrastructure. This made it suitable for this project which, by nature, handles large amounts of data. SQLite was chosen for lightweight relational storage, due to low resource overhead. Both technologies operate without a database server, contributing to the self-containment of the system.

Data handling and analysis is performed using the Pandas library (v2.3.3), providing efficient in-memory processing and manipulation, allowing for vectorised operations to be applied to large datasets.

3.5.3 Virtualisation

The manual auth.log data was collected using Linux systems on VirtualBox, allowing for isolated machines to be configured. By using publicly available Linux operating systems, the data that the system was built around is realistic to what's found in real-world environments.

3.6 Limitations

The project's limitations owe to various constraints, methodological decisions, or scope. The datasets, whilst generated with authenticity in mind, have nonetheless been generated artificially, so may not fully represent the complexity or variety of real-world files (Bergner and Landes 2025). Ground truth labels exist at event level; however, the rule engine aggregates events into alerts, preventing event-level classification from being compared directly. This prevents calculation of exact false positive and negative rates, but they can be inferred through comparison of event totals for ground truth against system output.

The focus of this system is authentication-related event detection, which does not represent all possible intrusion types against host systems.

With the chosen gap being functionality and performance in lightweight and constrained environments, emphasis was placed on this over detection capabilities. Consequently, whilst this project demonstrates the potential feasibility of this type of system, more extensive evaluation using real-world data and varied attack methods would be needed to declare this conclusively.

4 System Design

4.1 System Architecture

The system has been constructed as a lightweight HIDS, designed to ingest and analyse Linux authentication logs and identify suspicious activity. A modular construction separates components for UI, processing, analysis, and persistence.

4.1.1 Layer Breakdown

Three sections make up the layered architecture. The presentation layer handles user interaction and display, powered by Streamlit. Key actions include uploading a new file and viewing detected alerts within the GUI.

The logic layer provides file ingestion and applies the rule engine, whilst coordinating communication between the GUI and database.

Lastly, the data persistence layer allows for storage of scan metadata, event data for each scan, and the rules utilised in the rule engine. A hybrid database design was chosen to allow for efficient retrieval of scans and surface-level details, with larger amounts of event data being stored separately for scalable and optimised querying.

4.1.2 Modularity

The modular architecture allows for each component to be independent, promoting maintainability and extensibility. The diagram below summarises the interactions between the system's modules and the data pipeline.

Figure 3: Component Diagram for the HIDS Application

`gui.py` serves as the central point to the application and controls the flow to other pages, using each page's `.render()`.

`dashboard.py` displays an overview of the system and allows new files to be uploaded for scanning.

`processing.py` takes the uploaded file, stored within the session, and calls `log_parser.py` via `parse_auth_log.()` to ingest and standardise its content.

This is stored in the database using `db.py`'s `insert_scan_and_events()`. Next in the flow is `results.py`, which retrieves stored events and active rules using `load_events()` and `list_enabled_rules()`, respectively.

These are utilised in `rules_engine.py`'s `execute_all_rules()` to detect matching activity.

Lastly, `rules.py` handles all rule creation, reading, updating and deletion, with changes stored in the database.

4.2 Application Architecture

Figure 4: Application Flow Diagram

The system has been constructed as a multipage web application, with Dashboard, Processing, Results, and Rules, having their own views.

The Dashboard is the entry point to the application, displaying previous scans and allowing users to upload new files for analysis.

This continues to Processing, where files are parsed and separated into events, stored in the database, and displayed for verification.

The last stage is Results, which applies the rules against the processed events and delivers the outcome, taking the form of statistics and graphs.

The final available page is Rules, which allows for management and creation of rules applied to each scan. This is achieved using a user-friendly GUI form, instead of by editing complex configuration files.

This paged layout was chosen to guide the user through the key workflow stages in a directed and ordered manner.

4.3 Database Design

The system uses a hybrid database approach to efficiently handle scan metadata, as well as large volumes of associated event data. This addresses the strengths and necessities of each type of data.

4.3.1 Database 1: Relational

A relational database, powered by SQLite, stores information for each scan like filenames, timestamps, and summary statistics. It also stores any currently defined rules, with name, type, severity and set parameters.

4.3.2 Database 2: Analytical

An analytical database, powered by DuckDB, stores individual events after they are parsed. Each scan contributes potentially several hundred megabytes (for logs in the 1M+ line range), so this allows for this volume to be accommodated whilst maintaining quick storage and retrieval. Each event has values for fields like timestamp, type, source IP, and username. Each file that is processed is given a unique identifier key, linking it to corresponding metadata in the relational database.

4.3.3 Database EERD

Figure 5: Enhanced Entity-Relationship Diagram (EERD) for the HIDS Application

Each new scan creates an entry in the SCANS table of the SQLite database, containing information such as the filename, upload date, and start/end timestamp. Summary statistics are also included, like the number of users and IPs, and malicious activity counts, which are used on the dashboard to avoid having to recalculate them frequently. This is linked to the DuckDB database by the .duckdb's filename being the scan_id from the SCANS table. The EVENTS table contains an entry for each row in the imported log, with separate entities for timestamp, IP, username, event type, and raw line. Lastly, the SQLite database also stores the RULES table, with entities for the name and parameters.

4.4 Rule Engine Design

The core of the application's function is the rule engine, which takes a scan's parsed events and applies any active rules against it.

The rules have parameters to define a pattern of potentially malicious behaviour, and are stored in the database for management by the user. Each rule includes a unique identifier, type, severity, and triggering conditions.

4.4.1 Rule Types

The types of rules available are threshold-based, which look for a frequency of certain events, and sequence-based, which detect certain events occurring in a particular order.

4.4.2 Functionality

During analysis on the results page, any enabled rules are loaded from the database and evaluated against the retrieved event data. Any matching rules trigger an alert with the associated severity level, which are shown once all events have been analysed.

This cause-and-effect system allows for the events that triggered the alert to be evidenced, allowing for clear understanding when the user is analysing the results.

4.5 Data Flow

Figure 6: Data pipeline diagram showing how a .log file is analysed

The log is processed through a structured data pipeline with several key stages.

4.5.1 Upload, Parsing & Standardisation

Firstly, the file is uploaded from the dashboard. The file is then passed to the processing page where each line is parsed, and using regular expression matching, has key data extracted such as timestamp, username, source IP, event type, and authentication outcome. This data is then standardised into the desired format, ensuring that data follows a consistent schema. Lastly, the standardised data is stored in the database; summary information and metadata into the relational database, and event data into the analytical database.

4.5.2 Analysis & Results

If they wish, the user can return to the dashboard and the data is still stored. However, the intended flow is to continue to the results page immediately. The scan's data is retrieved from

the databases and processed against the rules engine, with the outcome being displayed on the results page. Triggered alerts are aggregated in a summary view and options for data exploration are offered.

A user can select a previous scan from the dashboard, skipping the uploading and processing stages, going straight to results. This reapplies the rule engine using the latest version of the stored rules.

Figure 7 shows the sequence of operations performed during log analysis, viewing previous scans, and managing rules.

Figure 7: Sequence Diagram for the HIDS Application

4.6 User Interaction Planning

4.6.1 Purpose

The system aims to provide a guided flow from beginning to end, allowing for non-technical users to analyse files without coding knowledge or having to edit configuration files.

4.6.2 Dashboard GUI

Figure 8: Dashboard Wireframe

The UI begins at the Dashboard, which allows for the results of an existing scan to be viewed, or a new file uploaded for analysis. After uploading a file, the user can proceed to Processing, which parses and stores the scan data.

4.6.3 Processing GUI

Figure 9: Processing Page Wireframe

4.6.4 Results GUI

This then leads into Results, where the user is shown the outcome of the rules being applied. The results are broken down into several formats, including graphical and tabular data views. Key malicious events are highlighted and visible at a glance.

Figure 10: Results Page Wireframe

4.6.5 Rule Management GUI

The system's rule management page allows for rules to be added or edited. This offers accessibility benefits, versus requiring direct editing of underlying configuration files, which has the chance of introducing errors.

Figure 11: Rule Management Page Wireframe

4.6.6 Use Case Diagram

Figure 12 presents the main user interactions of the system.

Figure 12: Use Case Diagram for the HIDS Application

The sole actor is the user, who can upload and scan a log file. Additional tasks include viewing previous scans and managing the rules used during analysis.

5 Implementation and Results

The project repository is available at:

<https://github.com/harryderouich/FinalProject> (Derouich 2026)

5.1 Log Parsing

5.1.1 Regular Expression Matching

First, log ingestion and parsing functionality was developed, capable of extracting relevant information from an uploaded `auth.log` file. These files contain raw text that is generated by the Linux `sshd` service upon authentication events. This was achieved using regular expression (regex) matching statements which identifies if a line contains a desired event. Several regex patterns were created for this project, matching failed logins, successful logins, or attempts to access user accounts that do not exist. For each match, relevant details are extracted using string splitting and methods from the Python `re` module. The result is a line from an `auth.log` file being transformed into a structured event record, containing timestamp, type, source IP, and username, allowing for rule evaluation in later stages.

5.1.2 Parsing Considerations

Regex operations are computationally expensive to apply to every line, greatly increasing the processing time of large datasets. To combat this, filtering is performed early on to discard any lines in the log not containing authentication events, only applying the regular expression matching to remaining lines. This optimisation supports lightweight performance objectives by greatly reducing processing time.

In summary, the processing pipeline consists of the pre-filter, regex matching, event extraction, and conversion to structured output. This staged approach ensures that computational power is not wasted and that only relevant authentication remain.

5.2 Event Standardisation

Due to the lack of logging system standardisation among Linux distributions, the exact format of the `auth.log` files can differ between systems. A standardisation stage was implemented to enforce a strict and common schema, ensuring that logic will work reliably from the parsing stage onwards. This is where the Pandas library is first introduced, allowing for data to be manipulated into the desired format. The result of standardisation is consistency of log entries, allowing for reliable processing during later stages. Enforcing a fixed schema allows for deterministic output from the logic layer, without further data clean up.

5.2.1 Operations

The timestamp is standardised into a common format and other mandatory attributes are checked for compliance. Invalid entries are removed to ensure that the resulting data is complete and valid. The result is a structured, compliant dataframe that can be reliably used in further stages of the program, with a reduced likelihood of parsing errors influencing detection outcomes.

5.3 Database Persistence

5.3.1 Hybrid Design Motivation

A persistence layer was implemented to store previous scans. A hybrid approach uses two technologies to store scan metadata and complete event data. This was adopted to prevent performance degradation with increasing amounts of data. Earlier in development, all data was stored in a single relational database. However, during performance testing, the database insertion and query time was found to increase exponentially with the size of the database, resulting in poor scaling.

To combat this, the database layer was reconstructed using a hybrid approach, utilising a fast relational database (using SQLite) for scan metadata and rules, with a separate analytical database (powered by DuckDB) for bulk data storage. This balanced queryability, when displaying a list of scans on the dashboard or retrieving rules, with larger-scale queries of event data (when the rule engine is applied) being optimised. By separating this data, CRUD operations can occur efficiently as the database size increases, mitigating the earlier bottleneck. This supports the project's requirement for scalable and predictable performance in constrained environments.

5.3.2 Coordinating the Hybrid Database

These databases are linked by a unique identifier for each scan, which connects scan metadata with its parsed events. The metadata stored for each scan includes filename, time span, and summary statistics. The analytical data is appended to using bulk insertion operations, removing the need for individual entries to be inserted individually when working with large datasets. This database architecture allows for the system to handle large data volumes.

5.4 Rule Engine

The system's core are its rules and how they are applied against ingested logs. This impacts threat detection, influencing system accuracy. Initially, several hard-coded rules were written into the program's logic to establish parsing functionality. As dictated by the project aim, this was extended to allow for user configurable rules, providing control and flexibility over what returns an alert.

5.4.1 Rule Features

Rules provide the conditions indicating malicious behaviour, including which event type to monitor, after how many an alert should trigger, and the time window to examine. An example is a threshold rule that triggers if there are ≥ 5 failed logins from the same IP within 1 minute, identifying a high frequency of authentication events (a possible brute force attempt). The rule engine loads the parsed events and enabled rules from the database. Each rule is evaluated sequentially over each event and a match is returned if the conditions are met. Rules are applied against time-grouped event data, allowing for frequency to impact whether an alert should be triggered.

5.4.2 Configuration Options

The first rule type is a threshold rule. This sets an event type, threshold, and time frame to trigger the alert. For instance, ≥ 5 `login_fail` events within 1 minute should trigger an alert, potentially indicating a brute force attempt.

The second rule type is a sequence rule, which looks for a certain event type to be followed by another type of event. For example, a `login_fail` followed by a `login_success`, indicating an intrusion may have occurred. During early baseline testing, this rule type would sometimes return high over-detection of events, triggered by genuine password fail/s, followed by the correct password.

This led to a 'threshold-sequence' rule type to be developed, which works like a sequence rule, whilst allowing for a threshold to be set for the preceding event. This allowed for a more robust rule like ≥ 5 `login_fail` events, followed by a `login_success` event, which may more accurately reflect a successful brute force intrusion due to the higher volume of `login_fails`. Implementing this rule type was necessary to reduce over-detection within baseline datasets. This improves reliability and accuracy of the detection algorithm and demonstrates the iterative approach that developed the detection logic.

5.4.3 Alert Explainability & Drawbacks

When a rule triggers an alert it includes the timestamp, which rule triggered, and causal evidence. This allows for system transparency and can aid analysts in further exploring the activity. Generated alerts are passed to the results page for aggregation and display.

The rule engine converts event sequences into corresponding alerts. At this stage, some granularity of individual events is lost as these are aggregated into alerts and overall counts. These totals can be examined and compared against the ground truth, but 1:1 mapping of events is not possible. As a result, malicious event under or over-estimation can be evaluated, but exact false positive or negative rates cannot.

5.5 Unit Testing and Validation

Unit tests were written to continuously validate the system's behaviour during development. Their scope includes log parsing, ensuring that events are extracted correctly, rule evaluation, to check alerts would be triggered correctly, and selected edge cases, such as empty rows or malformed data.

The tests use synthetic inputs, allowing for expected outputs to be determined. The actual results were asserted to ensure matching, indicating the function was working correctly. Testing uses the `pytest` framework, allowing for automated testing.

21 tests were written, which all pass in the latest version of the system. This testing methodology allowed for unintended bugs introduced when working on the system's modular design to be quickly addressed.

5.6 User Interface Implementation

5.6.1 Purpose & Technology Rationale

A GUI was implemented to allow for user interaction, rather than through the command line interface. The GUI for this system is powered by Streamlit, which provides a modern, interactive interface within a web browser. As a data-driven system, Streamlit was suitable thanks to it being primarily designed for data science related apps. This allowed the project to be written solely in Python, avoiding a separate frontend language from being integrated.

5.6.2 Initial Steps

Initial set up of the library saw the creation of the core sections of the multipage app; Dashboard, Processing, and Results, with linear flow between them. This was later extended, using persistence, to allow for alternative routes, such as processing a file, returning to the dashboard, and choosing to view the results later. By separating Processing and Results, the interface closely mimics the underlying system operations, increasing transparency and clarity.

5.6.3 Dashboard UI Implementation

Figure 13: Implementation of the Dashboard using Streamlit

The Dashboard is the starting point in the application, providing a list of any scans stored in the database, and allowing a new file to be uploaded for analysis.

Figure 14: A new file being uploaded from the Dashboard

5.6.4 Processing UI Implementation

Figure 15: Implementation of the Processing page, showing a successfully processed file

Uploading a file allows for continuation to the Processing page, where it's parsed, standardised and saved to the database, with the resulting dataset presented for verification.

5.6.5 Results UI Implementation

(a) Aggregated alerts and event breakdown

(b) Full list of alert and events

Figure 16: Implementation of the Results page alerting

The final step is the Results page, which loads the scan from the database and applies the rules using the rule engine, outputting detected alerts, activity visualisations, what caused the alerts, and a raw event output.

(a) Event Volume Graph

(b) Alert Distribution Charts

Figure 17: Two of the available six activity visualisations on the Results page

5.6.6 Rule Management UI Implementation

(a) List of Current Rules

(b) Creating a new rule form

Figure 18: Implementation of the Rule Management system using Streamlit

The Rules page was created when hard-coded rules were redesigned to allow user control. This bridges the rules, stored as YAML, and the user, allowing for creation and editing of rules without having to edit underlying configuration files, increasing the flexibility of the system. This improves user experience and accessibility, and reduces potential syntax error by preventing direct manipulation. Intra-system rule editing contributes to standalone functionality in isolated environments.

5.7 Challenges and Optimisation

5.7.1 Main Challenges

Challenges encountered surrounded performance and scalability as the system processed larger files. The system benefitted from baseline and malicious datasets influencing the logic development, so detection performance was high from the beginning. However, when larger files (100k-1M rows) were processed in succession, several oversights were clear.

5.7.2 Parsing Challenges

The event parsing, using regex, is the most computationally expensive stage of analysis. Whilst suitable for consistently formatted data, when performed on every row this introduced significant overhead. Diagnostics irrelevant to authentication ('noise') sometimes formed a large part of ingested files.

This was improved using filtering, following data upload and preceding regex operations. This performed lighter operations like dropping empty lines, skipping lines missing the `sshd` keyword (indicating they are not part of the SSH service), and ignoring lines under a minimum length (indicating they're malformed or irrelevant to authentication). In some cases, upwards of 50% of rows in the uploaded test files were 'noise', providing a proportional time saving. This improved scalability due to lowered processing times.

5.7.3 Persistence Challenges

When testing at scale, database insertion and query speed introduced problems. When database size grew (after many large scans), performance lowered. This influenced the hybrid solution, with event storage being transferred to DuckDB. Database insertion and querying is no longer impeded by database size, as each scan's events are stored in separate files. Consequently, the system can cope with larger logs without performance degrading.

5.7.4 Minor Optimisations

Other optimisations involved retrieving and caching files as few possible times, and avoiding repeated calls to analysis functions between pages. These optimisations allow the system to process larger datasets whilst maintaining performance, which aligns with the performance aims set out in the evaluation framework.

5.8 Detection Evaluation

The detection effectiveness must be assessed to determine suitability of the system for its purpose. This is the system's ability to correctly distinguish (at aggregate level) between benign and malicious activity within a log. This was evaluated by testing the system against baseline datasets, representing benign activity, and a dataset containing attacks, representing malicious activity.

For the synthetic datasets, ground truth is generated at the event level, allowing for 1:1 mapping of generated events as malicious or benign. However, once the system processes the events into alerts, 1:1 mapping of event results back to ground truth is lost. This limits evaluation to being performed at the aggregate level. Using the synthetic datasets and their ground truth, the aggregate agreement can be assessed without aligning each individual event. Event counts

can be compared to give the overall relative deviation, indicating under and over-detection tendencies.

5.9 Detection Results

5.9.1 Generalised Detection Accuracy & Scalability

Filename	Alerts	FAILED LOGIN SPIKE	BRUTE BURST	INVALID USER ATTEMPTS	SUCCESS AFTER FAILS
baseline_100k.log	0	0	0	0	0
baseline_250k.log	0	0	0	0	0
baseline_500k.log	0	0	0	0	0
baseline_1m.log	0	0	0	0	0
bruteforce_100k.log	398	121	121	121	35
bruteforce_250k.log	950	291	292	291	76
bruteforce_500k.log	1965	602	600	595	168
bruteforce_1m.log	3857	1182	1178	1171	326

Table 2: Alert Summary of baseline and brute force files (100k-1M rows)

The observed behaviour was that the baseline files returned no alerts, with the malicious logs returning a proportional number of alerts. This indicates that the system can successfully differentiate behaviour at the dataset level.

5.9.2 Event Parsing Accuracy

bruteforce_100k		
Event	Ground Truth Total	System Total
login_fail	40,484	40,484
invalid_user	17,492	17,492
login_success	5,851	5,851

Table 3: Detected Events bruteforce_100k

bruteforce_250k		
Event	Ground Truth Total	System Total
login_fail	101,206	101,206
invalid_user	43,543	43,543
login_success	14,880	14,880

Table 4: Detected Events bruteforce_250k

bruteforce_500k		
Event	Ground Truth Total	System Total
login_fail	202,719	202,719
invalid_user	87,045	87,045
login_success	29,758	29,758

Table 5: Detected Events bruteforce_500k

bruteforce_1m		
Event	Ground Truth Total	System Total
login_fail	405,925	405,925
invalid_user	173,447	173,447
login_success	59,168	59,168

Table 6: Detected Events bruteforce_1m

The tables above show the true count of each event (derived from ground truth), and the output of the system after parsing. Across all datasets, the parsed event totals match the ground truth totals exactly, indicating that event parsing and attribution is performed correctly by the system. This validation applies only to event parsing and attribution, rather than malicious classification at this stage.

5.9.3 Malicious Activity Detection

bruteforce_100k				
Event	Ground Truth Malicious	Results Malicious	Malicious Difference	Error Rate
login_fail	39,977	39,977	0	0.0000%
invalid_user	17,267	17,267	0	0.0000%
login_success	21	35	14	66.6667%

Table 7: Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_100k

bruteforce_250k				
Event	Ground Truth Malicious	Results Malicious	Malicious Difference	Error Rate
login_fail	99,980	99,977	-3	-0.0030%
invalid_user	43,000	42,994	-6	-0.0140%
login_success	50	76	26	52.0000%

Table 8: Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_250k

bruteforce_500k				
Event	Ground Truth Malicious	Results Malicious	Malicious Difference	Error Rate
login_fail	200,220	200,208	-12	-0.0060%
invalid_user	85,980	85,963	-17	-0.0198%
login_success	115	168	53	46.0870%

Table 9: Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_500k

bruteforce_1m				
Event	Ground Truth Malicious	Results Malicious	Malicious Difference	Error Rate
login_fail	401,018	401,007	-11	-0.0027%
invalid_user	171,382	171,348	-34	-0.0198%
login_success	231	326	95	41.1255%

Table 10: Ground Truth vs. Malicious Event Detection — bruteforce_1m

The ground truth files and the system's results page show the number of events attributed as malicious or benign. The aggregated malicious event counts of ground truth and system output can be compared, with the difference indicating under (-) or over-detection (+). This can be represented as a percentage of the overall total of that particular event to represent relative deviation.

For the more deterministic threshold rules applied to `login_fail` and `invalid_user` events, these show near-perfect agreement, with minimal underestimation by the system (<0.02%). Under-detection by the system indicates false negative tendency.

Events using sequence-based rules, such as `login_success`, show a systematic over-detection of 41-67% owing to sequence aggregation mechanics. Over-detection by the system indicates false positive tendency.

The relative deviation is inflated due to the small base rate of malicious `login_success` events. This is seen by an over-detection of 14 events returning a 66% relative deviation (vs. 21 truly malicious events), whereas a deviation of ~0.24% is observed when compared to the total 5,851 `login_success` events.

In summary, detection of malicious `login_fail` and `invalid_user` events aligns closely with ground truth, with minimal deviation of <0.02%. Detection of `login_success` events is overestimated due to over-attribution of sequence-based patterns. This behaviour is consistent across dataset sizes. Due to the limitations identified in Section 3.6 and 5.4.3, the loss of 1:1 event mapping after alert abstraction prevents calculation of exact false positive and negative rates.

5.10 Performance Evaluation

Evaluating system performance examines the processing capabilities and scalability for datasets of increasing size. Performance is a key part of this project's objective, so testing occurred continuously and influenced development. Timing and resource monitoring functions were added to provide diagnostics on the stages of the program's flow. This was used during troubleshooting of particularly slow sections and when calculating the total processing time of a file.

To test performance at scale, processing time was measured for datasets 100,000 to 1,000,000 rows in size. Synthetic datasets with both baseline and attack scenarios were used. Evaluation criteria looked at two metrics; total execution time, and average CPU usage during the processing and analysis pipeline. The tests were conducted multiple times, and an average taken, to increase the results' reliability and allow for fluctuations in system resource availability. Scalability was assessed using proportionally increasing dataset sizes. Successful performance was classified as processing time increasing linearly, and CPU usage remaining consistent, as dataset size grew.

5.11 Performance Results

5.11.1 Test Conditions

Testing was programmatically timed using `psutil`. Full test conditions can be found in Appendix A.

5.11.2 Processing Time & CPU Usage

With datasets spanning 100,000-1,000,000 rows, it can be seen that the processing time progresses approximately linearly, showing that earlier optimisations prevented the exponential time growth relating to database size. Near-linear scaling indicates controlled scalability and allows for performance to be forecasted, aligning with the project's requirement for predictable performance.

CPU average remains consistent across file size, indicating that the system does not degrade with larger files. The system confirms that it operates within lightweight design constraints, processing large amounts of data on consumer-grade hardware without significant performance degradation.

Rows	Baseline Time (s)	Bruteforce Time (s)	CPU Avg
100k	2.878	1.996	100.40%
250k	3.838	3.488	102.40%
500k	4.85	5.456	104%
1M	5.482	7.876	104%

Table 11: Testing data for 100,000 to 1,000,000 row log files

6 Discussion

6.1 System Performance

Figure 19: Graph of processing time and CPU usage for baseline and bruteforce logs (100k to 1M rows)

6.1.1 Linear Scalability

Evidence from testing described in Section 5.11 shows that processing time increases approximately linearly with dataset size, indicating controlled linear scaling. The requirement for predictable performance in a constrained environment has been successfully met.

This contrasts earlier versions of system architecture, which increased exponentially with dataset size, showing successful mitigation through the optimisations chosen. With the hybrid database architecture separating bulk event storage, performance does not degrade as storage requirements increase.

The pre-filtering stage that occurs before regex evaluation eliminates unnecessary computation, significantly reducing processing time. Filtering operations take less time compared to regex matching, resulting in a time saving nearly proportional to the amount of 'noise' rows (i.e. 40% 'noise' reduces processing time by almost 40%).

6.1.2 Resource Stability

CPU usage remaining consistent with dataset size indicates stable resource utilisation. 1,000,000 rows represents a realistic size from systems with high uptime or frequent access. With completion in 5.5-8 seconds on consumer hardware, this reinforces the objective of creating a lightweight and scalable HIDS. The system demonstrates viability on non-enterprise hardware, without performance being significantly impacted.

The project's aim of producing a lightweight solution for threat detection has been met with the above testing. A trade-off was chosen for this level of performance, prioritising speed over analysis depth.

6.2 Effectiveness of Rule-based Detection

6.2.1 Malicious Results Validation

Figure 20: Screenshot of the HIDS application showing successful detection of threats

The system successfully detects several examples of malicious activity, including brute force and user enumeration, with nearly 400 alerts generated for `bruteforce_100k.log`. Detection performance is enhanced using event correlation, rather than analysing events in isolation. Threshold and sequence rule types allow for modelling of realistic threat patterns using parameters. Running analysis multiple times on the same data results in identical alerts being triggered, indicating deterministic output.

6.2.2 Alert Evidence & Transparency

	ts_utc	rule_id	rule_name	severity	src_ip	user	evidence
0	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	rule_invalid_user_attempts	INVALID_USER_ATTEMPTS - Enumerati	HIGH	192.168.56.101	None	15 invalid_user in 1min
1	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	rule_brute_burst	BRUTE_BURST - High Speed Brute Forc	HIGH	192.168.56.101	None	54 login_fail in 1min
2	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	rule_failed_login_spike	FAILED_LOGIN_SPIKE - Multiple failed l	MED	192.168.56.101	None	54 login_fail in 5min
3	2026-01-22 09:00:00+00:00	rule_invalid_user_attempts	INVALID_USER_ATTEMPTS - Enumerati	HIGH	192.168.56.101	None	188 invalid_user in 1min
4	2026-01-22 09:00:00+00:00	rule_brute_burst	BRUTE_BURST - High Speed Brute Forc	HIGH	192.168.56.101	None	421 login_fail in 1min
5	2026-01-22 09:00:00+00:00	rule_failed_login_spike	FAILED_LOGIN_SPIKE - Multiple failed l	MED	192.168.56.101	None	421 login_fail in 5min
6	2026-01-22 09:01:00+00:00	rule_invalid_user_attempts	INVALID_USER_ATTEMPTS - Enumerati	HIGH	192.168.56.101	None	178 invalid_user in 1min
7	2026-01-22 09:01:00+00:00	rule_brute_burst	BRUTE_BURST - High Speed Brute Forc	HIGH	192.168.56.101	None	407 login_fail in 1min
8	2026-01-22 09:01:00+00:00	rule_failed_login_spike	FAILED_LOGIN_SPIKE - Multiple failed l	MED	192.168.56.101	None	828 login_fail in 5min
9	2026-01-22 09:02:00+00:00	rule_invalid_user_attempts	INVALID_USER_ATTEMPTS - Enumerati	HIGH	192.168.56.101	None	148 invalid_user in 1min

Figure 21: Screenshot of the HIDS application showing evidence for the triggered alerts for bruteforce_100k.log

Triggered alerts can be traced back to what it matched to. The list of alerts and their evidence are shown above, with 'INVALID_USER_ATTEMPTS' being triggered by '15 invalid_user in 1min', where the threshold is ≥ 5 . Alert traceability promotes transparency and auditability, allowing for meaningful incident response actions.

6.2.3 Benign Results Validation

Figure 22: Screenshot of the HIDS application showing zero triggered alerts for baseline_100k.log

When analysing a baseline file, zero alerts are returned, which is expected behaviour when there has been no malicious activity. This indicates distinguishing of malicious and benign activity within the test scenarios.

6.2.4 Accuracy Validation & Critique

The system showed negligible deviation in detecting malicious login_fail and invalid_user events ($< 0.02\%$), likely due to events occurring near correlation window edges.

The `login_success` event was consistently over-detected by the system (41-67%). However, the absolute impact is smaller (0.16-0.24% of total events). This could be caused by the generation script sharing IPs for generating attacks and benign events. Whilst realistic for attack behaviour, a benign login success following an attack from the same IP would be classified as malicious. Incorrect `login_success` detections increase proportionally with dataset size, showing systematic behaviour.

Figure 23: Screenshots of the HIDS application's rule management system

6.2.5 Assessing Rule Management

A user manageable rule system allows for on-the-fly rule management without the user having to modify underlying code. This boosts adaptability and increases system flexibility. The results demonstrate that detection of malicious activity is feasible with a rule-based system, without machine learning. Sequence rules functionality was extended into sequence-threshold, after testing showed over-detection. A rule-based system can deliver strong results for known patterns but exhibits sensitivity to rule design, mandating careful parameter selection. A downside of this approach is that attacks different to the predefined patterns won't be detected, a known limitation. This reinforces the importance of rule design in system effectiveness.

6.2.6 Reliability & Testing

The system's deterministic output allowed for verification using unit testing. This validated that events were parsed correctly and that rules were triggered as intended. The unit tests used synthetic data and a ground truth to confirm component-level functionality. This showed consistent performance, supporting expected output within controlled conditions.

6.3 Comparison with Machine Learning-based IDS

6.3.1 Benefits & Avoided Drawbacks

A machine-learning approach to threat detection requires initial and ongoing training processes requiring large volumes of labelled datasets. With the system's rule system, this need is avoided.

Computational requirements of a rule-based approach are less than machine learning, as intensive processes (e.g. feature extraction, model inference) do not occur.

This system is simpler to deploy, as it doesn't require specialist hardware (e.g. GPUs) or model management pipelines to function. Contrasting with machine-learning, the rule-based system functions entirely offline, having zero reliance on the cloud for updates or intelligence.

Another benefit explainable alerting, whereas results from machine-learning algorithms are often opaque. This addresses the gap of a lightweight IDS, demonstrating suitability of a rule-based approach if computational power or connectivity is limited.

6.3.2 Restrictions vs. ML

The downside is that there isn't as much adaptability to unseen or novel attack patterns, likely underperforming in dynamic or complex threat environments. This demonstrates viability of the rule-based system when simplicity and transparency is the priority over the highest detection capabilities. This represents the trade-off between efficiency and adaptability.

6.4 Suitability for Constrained Environments

6.4.1 Self Containment

The system has been designed to have minimal dependencies, instead utilising self-contained and widely available technologies like Python, SQLite/DuckDB, and Pandas. As already mentioned, there is no connectivity requirement, making it suitable for isolated use. Processing occurs within the system running the application, meaning that data is not put under unnecessary risk, improving security compliance. As a self-contained system, it can operate without integration into existing/legacy network infrastructure. Consequently, maintenance is simplified and the attack surface against the system is reduced.

6.4.2 Performance-aware Functionality

Adopting a resource-aware design, the system performs well on low-powered hardware, demonstrating usability in consumer-grade or lightweight systems.

Alignment with the research gap of constrained environments is demonstrated through the system's high performance without dependency on the internet. Suitability is limited to scenarios where detection depth is a lower priority than the hardware or connectivity constraints, as the system's functionality lacks deeper analysis capabilities.

6.5 Limitations

6.5.1 Scope of Detection Capabilities

As the system was designed to analyse `auth.log` files, it's limited to detecting attacks through the authentication service, so cannot detect activity like file integrity violations or privilege

escalation attempts. This limits the system's effectiveness as a general purpose IDS. Only defined rules in the system are checked, resulting in novel attacks going undetected. A machine-learning approach could introduce anomaly-based detection, looking for subtle behaviour deviation, whereas the rule-based approach looks for exact behavioural matches. The rules themselves will become less effective over time, mandating ongoing monitoring and refinement to maintain effectiveness.

6.5.2 Rule Limitations

False positives occur when a user's behaviour closely mimics an attack (e.g. multiple genuine failed login attempts), with rules needing to be mindful of not introducing false negatives when trying to reduce false positives. This introduces a rule design trade-off of sensitivity vs. specificity.

6.5.3 Full Accuracy Evaluation

Whilst detection performance was evaluated using baseline and maliciously categorised files, as well as overall malicious event counts as ground truth, accuracy metrics such as false positive/negative rates were not investigated.

This is due to the system's inability to map malicious events 1:1 back to ground truth, with aggregated totals being the only metric for comparison. Whilst the ground truth file does granularly label whether each event was malicious, when the system generates alerts, the mapping of individual events is abstracted. This trade-off was a result of the system's processing pipeline, which at a certain stage had to sacrifice granularity to maximise performance at larger dataset sizes.

This demonstrates an approximation of detection performance, but does not fully evaluate accuracy in a real-world scenario.

6.5.4 Reliance on Synthetic Datasets

Synthetic datasets used for rule creation and testing do not represent the variance of real-world log data, but were chosen for project-related scope and feasibility constraints. Therefore, system performance could differ within a real-world deployment, partially reducing results confidence.

6.5.5 On-demand Scanning

As the system only handles ad-hoc scans and alerting, this limits it to passive monitoring, rather than as a full incident response solution.

6.5.6 Testing Limitations

Testing was limited to synthetic data, which despite best efforts, cannot fully represent real-world variability and noise. It only tests the system functionally and does not evaluate quantitative accuracy metrics such as false positive/negative. Unit testing also cannot evaluate how the system might perform against an unknown attack type, but this is a limitation of the rule-based approach itself. Unit tests were written for each component, so whilst their behaviour is validated, system-level operations and inter-component functionality is not. More extensive testing using real-world data would be required to fully establish system reliability.

6.6 Evaluation Against Aims

High performance on lightweight hardware was achieved, demonstrated by processing one million rows in <8 seconds in Section 6.1. Explainability was achieved each scan's alerts referencing the activity that triggered them, shown in Figure 20. Detection effectiveness was partially achieved due to the constraints of a rule-based logic system, shown by the difference between the results for malicious and benign logs in Figure 21 and 22. Lightweight performance and explainability came at the cost of detection depth and adaptability, an acknowledged trade-off.

The limitations outlined above demonstrate that, whilst the developed prototype does show effectiveness within its scope, it lacks suitability as a comprehensive security solution without further enhancements being applied.

7 Conclusion

7.1 Achievement of Aims

This project has successfully designed and implemented a lightweight HIDS, adhering to efficiency, simplicity, and explainability objectives. It has achieved its lightweight performance and explainability aims, and partially achieved its detection effectiveness aim.

Functionality to ingest, parse, and standardise `auth.log` files into a structured format, has been demonstrated, for use during analysis. The HIDS effectively detects common authentication-based attacks, including brute force and enumeration attempts, using user-configurable rules.

High performance has been shown through linear scaling using logs up to 1-million rows, whilst maintaining stable resource use. Scalability was demonstrated using controlled performance tests, showing proportional processing time as input data sizes increase.

The detection capabilities were evaluated, which demonstrated strong performance for threat identification, with limitations in correlation logic for sequence-based attacks. Explainability has been demonstrated through transparent rule design and well-evidenced alert generation.

This confirms that a rule-based approach to intrusion detection is viable in the intended resource-constrained or air-gapped environments, with limitations for detecting novel behaviour, showing that performance and explainability was achieved at the expense of detection depth and adaptability. This confirms suitability for ad-hoc detection in the targeted environments, but not as an all-encompassing security solution.

7.2 Key Contributions

The main contribution of the project is the development of a self-contained HIDS, specifically designed for the gap of lightweight and isolated environments.

The inclusion of the user-manageable rule system offers an accessible way to maintain rules over time, removing the need for configuration files editing, addressing the maintainability gap within offline networks.

The implementation of a hybrid database solution offers high-performance persistence that does not degrade as more scans are stored, addressing scalability. Empirical performance testing of datasets with increasing size evidences stable resource usage.

The rule-based system that was implemented offers transparent threat detection, with alerts indicating what caused them to trigger.

Combining these contributions demonstrates that a rule-based approach to intrusion detection delivers predictable, scalable, and transparent results within constrained environments.

7.3 Lessons Learned

Standardising the log was foundational to reliable functioning of the data pipeline. Decisions made for the system's architecture greatly affected the scalability of the system, demonstrating the impact architectural choices have.

Computationally expensive operations were shown to require close monitoring and optimisation to maintain performance. Complicating rule logic came at the expense of processing time,

against a requirement of this project.

Whilst synthetic datasets allowed for development of the system, they highlighted a need for verification against real-world-generated data to ensure the system can cope with this variety.

These lessons emphasise the need for performance-aware design to inform decisions early in development, and that validation using real-world data is a key to assessing viability.

7.4 Future Work

To fully evaluate threat detection effectiveness, the system could test real-world datasets to reinforce robustness claims. Formal accuracy metrics could be established by validating the system's event classification with ground truth, on an event-by-event basis.

System capabilities could be extended by adding support for other operating systems, or other application logs, over being limited to Linux authentication logs. The system could be incorporated into a broader SIEM solution for rolling, real-time monitoring and alerting capabilities.

Further performance optimisations that could be implemented include batching or parallel processing capabilities to improve scalability. Exploration into rule creation assistance, such as historic data allowing for feedback on a rule's effectiveness, could reduce the guesswork during parameter selection. The rules themselves could be strengthened by experimenting with tighter time windows to eliminate variance from events occurring at window edges.

A natural progression would be to examine a hybrid rule-ML approach to deliver a solution that offers rule-based transparency and machine-learning adaptability.

With that said, future work should initially focus on validation of the existing system using real-world data, before exploration into extending system scope is considered.

References

- Abad, C., J. Taylor, C. Sengul, W. Yurcik, Y. Zhou and K. Rowe (2003). ‘Log correlation for intrusion detection: a proof of concept’. In: *19th Annual Computer Security Applications Conference*, pp. 255–264.
- Axelsson, S. (2000). *Intrusion detection systems: a survey and taxonomy*. Technical Report 99-15. Chalmers University of Technology. [online] Available at: <https://www.cse.chalmers.se/~andrei/IDS.pdf> (Accessed: 17 November 2025).
- Bergner, K. and D. Landes (2025). ‘A uniform assessment of host-based intrusion detection data sets’. *Computers & Security*, 157, p. 104503. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2025.104503>.
- BlackFog (2023). *SMBs Were Victims of Cyberattack*. [online] Available at: <https://www.blackfog.com/smb-were-victims-cyberattack/> (Accessed: 17 April 2026).
- Bridges, R. A., T. R. Glass-Vanderlan, M. D. Iannacone, M. S. Vincent and Q. Chen (2019). ‘A survey of intrusion detection systems leveraging host data’. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 52(6), p. 128. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3344382>.
- Buczak, A. L. and E. Guven (2015). ‘A survey of data mining and machine learning methods for cyber security intrusion detection’. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 18(1), pp. 353–376. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2015.2494502>.
- Callegari, C., S. Giordano and M. Pagano (2024). ‘A real-time deep learning based approach for detecting network attacks’. *Computer Networks*, 240, p. 110168.
- Center for Internet Security (2019). *Log management guide*. [online] Available at: <https://www.cisecurity.org> (Accessed: 12 November 2025).
- DeepStrike (2024). *How Many Cyberattacks Happen Every Day?* [online] Available at: <https://deepstrike.io/blog/how-many-cyberattacks-happen-every-day> (Accessed: 17 April 2026).
- Derouich, H. (2026). *FinalProject GitHub Repository*. [online] Available at: <https://github.com/harryderouich/FinalProject> (Accessed: 21 April 2026).
- Fang, J. and F. Leng (2025). ‘Network Security Intrusion Detection System Based on Deep Learning’. *Procedia Computer Science*, 261, pp. 1107–1113.
- García-Teodoro, P., J. Díaz-Verdejo, G. Maciá-Fernández and E. Vázquez (2009). ‘Anomaly-based network intrusion detection: Techniques, systems and challenges’. *Computers & Security*, 28(1–2), pp. 18–28.
- Greitzer, F. L. and D. A. Frincke (2010). ‘Combining traditional cyber security audit data with psychosocial data: towards predictive modeling for insider threat mitigation’. In: *Advances in Information Security*. 49. Boston, MA: Springer, pp. 85–113. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-7133-3_5.
- Haas, S., R. Sommer and M. Fischer (2020). ‘Zeek-osquery: host-network correlation for advanced monitoring and intrusion detection’. In: *ICT Systems Security and Privacy Protection*. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 248–262. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58201-2_17.

- Harish, M., S. Lokesh, P. Sakthivel and B. Akshaya (2026). ‘Hybrid deep learning model for network intrusion detection using optimal feature fusion’. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 17(1), p. 103904.
- Hevner, A. R., S. T. March, J. Park and S. Ram (2004). ‘Design science in information systems research’. *MIS Quarterly*, 28(1), pp. 75–105.
- Hore, S., S. Biswas, A. Das and A. Mukherjee (2024). ‘A sequential deep learning framework for a robust and resilient network intrusion detection system’. *Computers & Security*, 138, p. 103515.
- IBM (2023). *Half of Breached Organizations Unwilling to Increase Security Spend Despite Soaring Breach Costs*. IBM Newsroom. [online] Available at: <https://newsroom.ibm.com/2023-07-24-IBM-Report-Half-of-Breached-Organizations-Unwilling-to-Increase-Security-Spend-Despite-Soaring-Breach-Costs> (Accessed: 17 April 2026).
- Ioulianou, P., V. Vassilakis and I. Moscholios (2018). ‘A signature-based intrusion detection system for the internet of things’. In: *2018 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*, pp. 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCC.2018.8538543>.
- Jansen, M., R. Bobba and D. Nevin (2024). ‘A comparative analysis of difficulty between log and graph-based detection rule creation’. In: *Proceedings of the 2024 Workshop on the Security of Objects (WoSoC)*, pp. 1–6.
- Javaid, A., Q. Niyaz, W. Sun and M. Alam (2016). ‘A deep learning approach for network intrusion detection system’. *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Security and Safety*, 3(9), e2.
- Jiang, J., H. Chu and D. Tian (2026). ‘A novel host-based intrusion detection approach leveraging audit logs’. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 174, p. 107995.
- Kolias, C., G. Kambourakis, A. Stavrou and J. Voas (2017). ‘DDoS in the IoT: Mirai and Other Botnets’. *Computer*, 50(7), pp. 80–84.
- Kong, J. H., L.-M. Ang and K. P. Seng (2015). ‘A comprehensive survey of modern symmetric cryptographic solutions for resource constrained environments’. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 49, pp. 15–50.
- Lippmann, R., D. J. Fried, I. Graf, J. W. Haines, K. R. Kendall, D. McClung, D. Weber, S. E. Webster, D. Wyschogrod, R. K. Cunningham and M. A. Zissman (2000). ‘Evaluating intrusion detection systems: the 1998 DARPA offline intrusion detection evaluation’. In: *Proceedings of the DARPA Information Survivability Conference and Exposition (DISCEX 2000)*. 2, pp. 12–26.
- Molnar, C., G. Casalicchio and B. Bischl (2020). ‘Interpretable machine learning – A brief history, state-of-the-art and challenges’. In: *ECML PKDD 2020 Workshops*. Springer International Publishing, pp. 417–431.
- National Institute of Standards and Technology (2015). *Guide to Industrial Control Systems (ICS) Security*. Technical Report SP 800-82. Revision 2. NIST. [online] Available at: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.800-82r2.pdf>.
- Osa, A., C. Ohaneme and C. Okeke (2024). ‘Design and implementation of a deep neural network approach for intrusion detection systems’. *Array*, 22, p. 100312.

- Palo Alto Networks Unit 42 (2020). *IoT Security Trends Report*. [online] Available at: <https://unit42.paloaltonetworks.com/iot-threat-report-2020/> (Accessed: 20 April 2026).
- Pandey, V., D. Sahu, S. Prakash, R. S. Rathore, P. Dixit and I. Hunko (2025). ‘A lightweight framework to secure IoT devices with limited resources in cloud environments’. *Scientific Reports*, 15, p. 98585.
- Parameshwarappa, P., Z. Chen and A. Gangopadhyay (2018). ‘Analyzing attack strategies against rule-based intrusion detection systems’. In: *Proceedings of the 33rd ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing (SAC)*, pp. 1–4.
- PC Kings (2020). *Internet of Things (IoT) devices illustration*. [online] Available at: <https://pckings.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/IoT.png> (Accessed: 17 April 2026).
- Raza, S., L. Wallgren and T. Voigt (2013). ‘SVELTE: Real-time intrusion detection in the internet of things’. *Ad Hoc Networks*, 11(8), pp. 2661–2674.
- Roesch, M. (1999). ‘Snort: lightweight intrusion detection for networks’. In: *Proceedings of the 13th USENIX Conference on System Administration (LISA '99)*, pp. 229–238. https://www.usenix.org/event/lisa99/full_papers/roesch/roesch.pdf.
- Saidi, F. (2025). ‘IDS-GPT: A Novel Deep Learning-Powered Framework for Network Traffic Intrusion Detection’. *Procedia Computer Science*, 270, pp. 1611–1620.
- Samek, W., T. Wiegand and K.-R. Müller (2017). ‘Explainable artificial intelligence: Understanding, visualizing and interpreting deep learning models’. *ITU Journal: ICT Discoveries*, 1(1). Special Issue: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Communication Networks and Services, pp. 1–10.
- Sinha, P., S. Prakash, S. K. Jha, V. Rathore, T. Yang, R. S. Rathore, A. Singh and R. Mishra (2023). ‘An efficient machine learning-based network intrusion detection system’. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 216, p. 103623.
- Siwach, M. and S. Mann (2022). ‘Anomaly detection for web log data analysis: A review’. *Journal of Algebraic Statistics*, 13, pp. 129–148.
- Sommer, R. and V. Paxson (2010). ‘Outside the closed world: On using machine learning for network intrusion detection’. In: *2010 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, pp. 305–316.
- Speculos (2023). *Air gap network topology*. [online] Available at: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Air_gap_network.png (Accessed: 17 April 2026).
- Statista (2022). *Expected Cost of Cybercrime Worldwide from 2022 to 2027*. [online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/chart/28878/expected-cost-of-cybercrime-until-2027/> (Accessed: 17 April 2026).
- Verizon (2025). *2025 Data Breach Investigations Report*. Verizon Business. [online] Available at: <https://www.verizon.com/business/resources/reports/dbir/> (Accessed: 17 April 2026).
- Verizon Business (2023). *Cloud Computing Security: Is It Safer Than On-Premises?* [online] Available at: <https://www.verizon.com/business/resources/articles/s/cloud-computing-security-is-it-safer-than-on-premises/> (Accessed: 17 April 2026).

Wahal, M., T. Choudhury and M. Arora (2018). 'Intrusion detection system in Python'. In: *2018 8th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence)*, pp. 348–353.

Zhou, Q., Y. Zhang, J. Liu and H. Wang (2025). 'A stacked machine learning-based intrusion detection system for smart connected vehicles'. *Symmetry*, 17(6), p. 874.

Zhu, B., A. Joseph and S. Sastry (2011). 'Taxonomy of cyber attacks on SCADA systems'. In: *2011 International Conference on Internet of Things and Cyber, Physical and Social Computing (iThings/CPSCoM)*, pp. 1–6.

A Experimental Setup and Environment

A.1 Hardware Specifications

Testing platform was a consumer-grade laptop with specifications below:

- Device: 2025 HONOR MagicBook Pro 14
- CPU: Intel® Core™ Ultra 5 processor 125H (14 cores)
- Memory: 24GB LPDDR5x 7467 MT/s
- Storage: 1TB SSD (Gen4 NVMe)

A.2 Software Specifications

- Windows 11
- Python 3.12
- Streamlit 1.54.0
- pandas 2.3.3
- SQLite 3.50.4
- DuckDB 1.4.4
- Plotly 6.6.0
- psutil 7.2.2
- numpy 2.4.2
- pytest 9.0.2

A.3 Test Conditions

Each dataset started with an empty database with 30 seconds of wait time between stages to decrease the likelihood of competing background processes impacting the performance of the system.

Each test was a fresh run using a newly uploaded file, rather than using data already in the session cache.

All testing was run with the laptop plugged into mains power to prevent power-saving mode from reducing the CPU power. This allowed for all tests to have a consistent level of processing power available.

Each test was run 5 times to allow for potential outliers and give a more representative average calculation.

A.4 Dataset Composition Summary

Filename	Total Rows	Total Auth Events	login_fail	invalid_user	login_success
baseline_100k.log	100000	25960	1978	828	23154
baseline_250k.log	250000	64580	4960	2103	57517
baseline_500k.log	500000	129493	9676	4214	115603
baseline_1m.log	1000000	259001	8294	19347	231360
bruteforce_100k.log	100000	63827	40484	17492	5851
bruteforce_250k.log	250000	159387	101155	43390	14842
bruteforce_500k.log	500000	319522	202719	87045	29758
bruteforce_1m.log	1000000	638540	405925	173447	59168

Table 12: Event Summary

Filename	Alerts	FAILED LOGIN SPIKE	BRUTE BURST	INVALID USER ATTEMPTS	SUCCESS AFTER FAILS
baseline_100k.log	0	0	0	0	0
baseline_250k.log	0	0	0	0	0
baseline_500k.log	0	0	0	0	0
baseline_1m.log	0	0	0	0	0
bruteforce_100k.log	398	121	121	121	35
bruteforce_250k.log	975	295	297	294	89
bruteforce_500k.log	1965	602	600	595	168
bruteforce_1m.log	3857	1182	1178	1171	326

Table 13: Alert Summary

B Rule Configuration

```
[rule_invalid_user_attempts] INVALID_USER_ATTEMPTS - Enumeration
  attempts
{
  "event_filter": "invalid_user",
  "threshold": 5,
  "window_minutes": 1,
  "group_by": [
    "src_ip"
  ]
}

[rule_failed_login_spike] FAILED_LOGIN_SPIKE - Multiple failed
  logins
{
  "event_filter": "login_fail",
  "threshold": 10,
  "window_minutes": 5,
  "group_by": [
    "src_ip"
  ]
}

[rule_success_after_fails] SUCCESS_AFTER_FAILS - Successful login
  after many failures
{
  "event_first": "login_fail",
  "threshold": 50,
  "event_second": "login_success",
  "window_minutes": 10,
  "group_by": [
    "src_ip"
  ]
}

[rule_brute_burst] BRUTE_BURST - High Speed Brute Force
{
  "event_filter": "login_fail",
  "threshold": 5,
  "window_minutes": 1,
  "group_by": [
    "src_ip"
  ]
}
```

C Example auth.log File

File: bruteforce_100k.log

Content: First 30 rows

63

```
2026-01-22T08:58:00+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session closed for user root
2026-01-22T08:58:00.040000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: testuser : TTY=pts/0 ; PWD=/home/testuser ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/usr/bin/systemctl restart ssh
2026-01-22T08:58:00.046000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session opened for user root(uid=0) by testuser(uid=1000)
2026-01-22T08:58:00.116000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[1653]: Received signal 15; terminating.
2026-01-22T08:58:00.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2503]: Server listening on 0.0.0.0 port 22.
2026-01-22T08:58:00.367471+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2503]: Server listening on :: port 22.
2026-01-22T08:58:20.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: gitlab : TTY=pts/0 ; PWD=/home/gitlab ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/usr/bin/systemctl restart ssh
2026-01-22T08:58:22.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2660]: Accepted password for builder from 10.0.0.22 port 32628 ssh2
2026-01-22T08:58:33.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[3902]: Accepted password for docker from 192.168.56.142 port 36907 ssh2
2026-01-22T08:58:40.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[1968]: Accepted password for deploy from 192.168.56.111 port 34360 ssh2
2026-01-22T08:58:46.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: testuser : TTY=pts/0 ; PWD=/home/testuser ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/usr/bin/systemctl restart ssh
2026-01-22T08:58:56.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[3557]: Accepted password for service from 10.0.0.90 port 36725 ssh2
2026-01-22T08:59:08.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session opened for user root(uid=0) by jenkins(uid=1000)
2026-01-22T08:59:16.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session opened for user root(uid=0) by developer(uid=1000)
2026-01-22T08:59:28.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2308]: Server listening on 0.0.0.0 port 22.
2026-01-22T08:59:28.367932+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2308]: Server listening on :: port 22.
2026-01-22T08:59:39.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session opened for user root(uid=0) by admin(uid=1000)
2026-01-22T08:59:50.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: ubuntu : TTY=pts/0 ; PWD=/home/ubuntu ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/usr/bin/systemctl restart ssh
2026-01-22T09:00:01.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4120]: Accepted password for sysadmin from 192.168.58.55 port 40147 ssh2
2026-01-22T09:00:06.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[1553]: Accepted password for deploy from 10.0.1.18 port 41948 ssh2
2026-01-22T09:00:16.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session closed for user root
2026-01-22T09:00:25.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session closed for user root
2026-01-22T09:00:29.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2285]: Accepted password for webuser from 10.0.1.75 port 34954 ssh2
2026-01-22T09:00:38.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[3458]: Accepted password for appuser from 192.168.58.225 port 34933 ssh2
2026-01-22T09:00:45.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2706]: Accepted password for builder from 192.168.57.23 port 30587 ssh2
2026-01-22T09:00:49.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session closed for user root
2026-01-22T09:00:53.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[1302]: Accepted password for service from 192.168.56.97 port 33922 ssh2
2026-01-22T09:00:59.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4355]: Server listening on 0.0.0.0 port 22.
2026-01-22T09:00:59.367587+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4355]: Server listening on :: port 22.
2026-01-22T09:01:05.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sudo: webuser : TTY=pts/0 ; PWD=/home/webuser ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/usr/bin/systemctl restart ssh
```

D Database Schema

D.1 Scans: data/app.db (SQLite)

```
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS scans (  
  scan_id      TEXT PRIMARY KEY,  
  filename     TEXT NOT NULL,  
  uploaded_at TEXT NOT NULL,  
  start_ts    TEXT,  
  end_ts      TEXT,  
  rows        INTEGER,  
  unique_ips  INTEGER,  
  unique_users INTEGER,  
  malicious_ct INTEGER DEFAULT 0,  
  unusual_ct  INTEGER DEFAULT 0  
);
```

D.2 Events: data/scans/<scan_id>.duckdb (DuckDB)

```
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS events (  
  ts_utc  VARCHAR,  
  src_ip  VARCHAR,  
  user    VARCHAR,  
  event   VARCHAR,  
  raw     VARCHAR  
);
```

D.3 Rules: data/app.db (SQLite)

```
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS rules (  
  rule_id      TEXT PRIMARY KEY,  
  rule_name    TEXT NOT NULL UNIQUE,  
  rule_type    TEXT NOT NULL,  
  severity     TEXT NOT NULL,  
  config       TEXT NOT NULL,  
  enabled      BOOLEAN DEFAULT 1,  
  created_at   TEXT NOT NULL,  
  updated_at   TEXT NOT NULL  
);
```

E Raw Data

E.1 Performance Timing

E.1.1 Baseline

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	0.47	2.49	2.96
2	0.44	2.25	2.69
3	0.44	2.41	2.85
4	0.45	2.50	2.95
5	0.43	2.51	2.94
Avg	0.446	2.432	2.878

Table 14: Baseline - 100k

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	0.86	3.03	3.89
2	0.84	3.03	3.87
3	0.85	2.91	3.76
4	0.86	2.88	3.74
5	0.88	3.05	3.93
Avg	0.858	2.980	3.838

Table 15: Baseline - 250k

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	1.92	3.31	5.23
2	1.27	3.69	4.96
3	1.34	3.49	4.83
4	1.26	3.24	4.50
5	1.08	3.65	4.73
Avg	1.374	3.476	4.850

Table 16: Baseline - 500k

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	2.18	3.47	5.65
2	1.95	3.69	5.64
3	2.00	3.50	5.50
4	2.10	3.23	5.33
5	2.00	3.29	5.29
Avg	2.046	3.436	5.482

Table 17: Baseline - 1M

E.1.2 Brute Force

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	0.67	1.42	2.09
2	0.65	1.29	1.94
3	0.61	1.26	1.87
4	0.62	1.41	2.03
5	0.62	1.43	2.05
Avg	0.634	1.362	1.996

Table 18: Bruteforce - 100k

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	1.29	2.46	3.75
2	1.32	2.31	3.63
3	1.09	2.28	3.37
4	1.11	2.25	3.36
5	1.07	2.26	3.33
Avg	1.176	2.312	3.488

Table 19: Bruteforce - 250k

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	2.03	3.95	5.98
2	2.17	3.31	5.48
3	1.93	3.27	5.20
4	1.97	3.32	5.29
5	2.18	3.15	5.33
Avg	2.056	3.400	5.456

Table 20: Bruteforce - 500k

Test	Processing	Results	Total
1	4.00	4.05	8.05
2	3.70	4.11	7.81
3	3.50	4.33	7.83
4	3.64	4.13	7.77
5	3.71	4.21	7.92
Avg	3.710	4.166	7.876

Table 21: Bruteforce - 1M

E.2 Alert Outputs

Abbreviated alert output for 100k brute force auth. log file (first 20 rows).

ts_utc	rule_id	severity	src_ip	user	evidence
2026-01-22 08:05	invalid_user_attempts	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	15 invalid_user / 1min
2026-01-22 08:05	brute_burst	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	54 login_fail / 1min
2026-01-22 08:05	failed_login_spike	MED	192.168.56.101	–	54 login_fail / 5min
2026-01-22 09:00	invalid_user_attempts	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	188 invalid_user / 1min
2026-01-22 09:00	brute_burst	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	421 login_fail / 1min
2026-01-22 09:00	failed_login_spike	MED	192.168.56.101	–	421 login_fail / 5min
2026-01-22 09:01	invalid_user_attempts	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	178 invalid_user / 1min
2026-01-22 09:01	brute_burst	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	407 login_fail / 1min
2026-01-22 09:01	failed_login_spike	MED	192.168.56.101	–	828 login_fail / 5min
2026-01-22 09:02	invalid_user_attempts	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	148 invalid_user / 1min
2026-01-22 09:02	brute_burst	HIGH	192.168.56.101	–	389 login_fail / 1min
2026-01-22 09:02	success_after_fails	MED	192.168.56.101	testuser	15114 fails → success / 10min
2026-01-22 09:02	failed_login_spike	MED	192.168.56.101	–	1217 login_fail / 5min
2026-01-22 09:03	failed_login_spike	MED	192.168.56.103	–	354 login_fail / 5min
2026-01-22 09:03	invalid_user_attempts	HIGH	192.168.56.103	–	184 invalid_user / 1min
2026-01-22 09:03	brute_burst	HIGH	192.168.56.103	–	354 login_fail / 1min
2026-01-22 09:04	failed_login_spike	MED	192.168.56.103	–	775 login_fail / 5min
2026-01-22 09:04	invalid_user_attempts	HIGH	192.168.56.103	–	204 invalid_user / 1min
2026-01-22 09:04	brute_burst	HIGH	192.168.56.103	–	421 login_fail / 1min
2026-01-22 09:05	brute_burst	HIGH	192.168.56.103	–	410 login_fail / 1min
2026-01-22 09:05	failed_login_spike	MED	192.168.56.103	–	1185 login_fail / 5min
...

Table 22: Detected authentication-related alerts

E.3 Event Detection Accuracy

bruteforce_100k	Ground Truth			Results			Malicious Difference	Error Rate
	Total	Malicious	Benign	Total	Malicious	Benign		
login_fail	40,484	39,977	507	40,484	39,977	507	0	0.0000%
invalid_user	17,492	17,267	225	17,492	17,267	225	0	0.0000%
login_success	5,851	21	5,830	5,851	35	5,816	14	66.6667%

Table 23: Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_100k.log

bruteforce_250k	Ground Truth			Results			Malicious Difference	Error Rate
	Total	Malicious	Benign	Total	Malicious	Benign		
login_fail	101,206	99,980	1,226	101,206	99,977	1,229	-3	-0.0030%
invalid_user	43,543	43,000	543	43,543	42,994	549	-6	-0.0140%
login_success	14,880	50	14,830	14,880	76	14,804	26	52.0000%

Table 24: Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_250k.log

bruteforce_500k	Ground Truth			Results			Malicious Difference	Error Rate
	Total	Malicious	Benign	Total	Malicious	Benign		
login_fail	202,719	200,220	2,499	202,719	200,208	2,511	-12	-0.0060%
invalid_user	87,045	85,980	1,065	87,045	85,963	1,082	-17	-0.0198%
login_success	29,758	115	29,643	29,758	168	29,590	53	46.0870%

Table 25: Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_500k.log

bruteforce_1m	Ground Truth			Results			Malicious Difference	Error Rate
	Total	Malicious	Benign	Total	Malicious	Benign		
login_fail	405,925	401,018	4,907	405,925	401,007	4,918	-11	-0.0027%
invalid_user	173,447	171,382	2,065	173,447	171,348	2,099	-34	-0.0198%
login_success	59,168	231	58,937	59,168	326	58,842	95	41.1255%

Table 26: Ground Truth vs Results for bruteforce_1m.log

F User Guide and Documentation

F.1 Installation & Getting Started

F.1.1 Prerequisites

- Python 3.8 or higher
- pip
- Streamlit
- pandas
- DuckDB
- SQLite
- Plotly
- psutil

F.1.2 Setup

1. Navigate to the project directory: `cd FinalProject`
 2. Install dependencies: `pip install -r requirements.txt`
 3. Run the application: `streamlit run gui.py`
 - The database initialises automatically on the first run
 - Default rules are added to the database if no rules exist
 - Opens in the default web browser at `http://localhost:8501`
 4. Baseline and malicious log files are provided in 'datasets/' for testing. Alternatively, generate your own logs using the log generation script (see Generating Logs section below).
-

F.2 User Guide

F.2.1 Dashboard

View past scans and upload new logs for analysis.

Viewing Past Scans

If any historic scans exist:

1. Use the dropdown to select a previous scan
2. Summary statistics and a graph preview will be displayed
3. To generate the graph, click the "Generate" button.
4. Options available for the scan include:
 - View detailed results: View the selected scan's results in full
 - Delete this scan: Permanently delete the selected scan from the database

Figure 24: Annotated screenshot of viewing past scans from the dashboard

Uploading New Logs

To upload a new log file for analysis:

1. At the bottom of the dashboard, use the file selector to either drag and drop a log file or click to browse your file system
2. Once a file has been selected, click “Process File” to start the analysis

Figure 25: Annotated screenshot uploading a new log file from the dashboard

Supported Formats

- SSH authentication logs (e.g., /var/log/auth.log)

Other Actions

- To delete all scans in the database, click the “Delete All Scans” button. Tick the confirmation checkbox to enable the button, then click it to permanently delete all scans from the database.
- To view and manage the rules in the database, click the “Manage Detection Rules” button. This will take you to the rule management page.

F.2.2 Processing

Process and parse data before analysis.

1. The uploaded file is read and processed to extract relevant authentication events. Any processing errors will be indicated at this stage.
2. The processed file is standardised and stored in the database.
3. Click “Continue to Results” to proceed to the results page.
4. Alternatively, click “Back to Dashboard” to return to the dashboard. The processed file has been stored in the database and its results can be accessed from the dashboard at a later time.

The screenshot shows a 'Processing' interface with a dark theme. At the top, it says 'Processing' with a small 'e3' icon. Below that, a box highlights 'Processing file: bruteforce_100k.log' with a red '1' next to it. A green bar below this box contains the message '✓ bruteforce_100k.log processed successfully'. Below the message is a table with 5 columns: 'ts_utc', 'src_ip', 'user', 'event', and 'raw'. The table contains 10 rows of data. At the bottom, two buttons are visible: 'Continue to Results' with a red '3' next to it, and 'Back to Dashboard' with a red '4' next to it.

	ts_utc	src_ip	user	event	raw
0	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	grafana	login_fail	2026-01-22T08:59:44.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2641]: Failed password for graf
1	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	postgres	invalid_user	2026-01-22T08:59:03.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4745]: Failed password for inva
2	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.111	deploy	login_success	2026-01-22T08:58:40.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[1968]: Accepted password for c
3	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	10.0.0.90	service	login_success	2026-01-22T08:58:56.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[3557]: Accepted password for s
4	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	daemon	login_fail	2026-01-22T08:59:59.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[3521]: Failed password for dae
5	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	www-data	login_fail	2026-01-22T08:59:57.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4020]: Failed password for ww
6	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	test	login_fail	2026-01-22T08:59:56.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4762]: Failed password for test
7	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	root	login_fail	2026-01-22T08:59:56.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[2808]: Failed password for root
8	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	elasticsearch	login_fail	2026-01-22T08:59:54.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4847]: Failed password for elas
9	2026-01-22 08:05:00+00:00	192.168.56.101	ftp	login_fail	2026-01-22T08:59:53.366000+00:00 victim-ubuntu sshd[4768]: Failed password for ftp f

Figure 26: Annotated screenshot of uploading a file being successfully processed

F.2.3 Results

View the results of a scan, including any alerts triggered by the detection rules.

1. The results page begins with the total HIGH or MED severity alerts being displayed at the top.
2. Next, a breakdown of events is shown (e.g. login_fail, login_success etc.)

Figure 27: Annotated screenshot of scan results showing alerts and event breakdown

3. Afterwards, a list of alerts broken down by rule is displayed, showing the number of times each rule was triggered.
4. Beneath this, a visualisation of the scans events is shown. The available graphs include:
 - Event volume: Shows the volume of events over time.
 - Alert timeline: Shows at what times alerts were triggered, colour coded by severity.
 - Attack flow: Shows the flow from IP address, to the rule/s it triggered, followed by severity and event type.
 - Rule heatmap: Shows a heatmap of alerts being triggered by hour of the day.
 - Top attackers: Shows the top 20 IPs responsible for triggering alerts and the number of alerts they triggered.
 - Alert Distribution: Shows the distribution of alerts by rule and severity.

Figure 28: Annotated screenshot of scan results showing alert breakdown and data visualisations

5. Under the graphs are summary statistics including how many events were processed, the failure rate, and the time span of the log file.
6. Next, “View alerts table” can be expanded to show a list of the individual alerts triggered with timestamp, which rule was matched, the source IP and what evidence caused it to trigger. This allows for the alert behaviour to be explainable. The alerts table can be exported as a CSV by clicking “Download alerts CSV”.
7. Lastly, expanding “View raw events” allows for the extracted events for the log file to be viewed in full, searched, and downloaded as a CSV.
8. Return to the dashboard by clicking “Back to Dashboard”. Alternatively, click “Manage Rules” to go to the rule management page.

Figure 29: Annotated screenshot of scan results showing summary statistics and raw data views

F.2.4 Rules

View, add, edit and delete detection rules used during analysis.

Viewing and Editing Rules

1. The rules page shows a list of all rules currently stored in the database.
2. From here, existing rules can be enabled or disabled using the checkbox toggle. Disabled rules will not trigger alerts during analysis.
3. Existing rules can be edited by clicking the pencil icon.
4. To delete a rule, click the bin icon. This will permanently delete the rule from the database.

Figure 30: Annotated screenshot of rules being viewed and edited

Adding New Rules

1. From the rule management page, click “Create New Rule” to open the new rule form.

Figure 31: Annotated screenshot of a new rule being created

2. Rule Type: Select the type of rule from the following options:
 - Threshold-Based: Triggers when an event exceeds a certain threshold within a specified time window
 - Sequence Detection: Triggers when one event type occurs, followed by another event type, in a specified time window
 - Threshold-Sequence: Triggers when an event exceeds a certain threshold, and is followed by another event type, within a specified time window
3. Fill in the form with the following information:
 - Rule Name: Type a name for the rule (e.g. Brute Force Attack)
 - Severity Level: Select the severity level for the rule (HIGH, MED, LOW)
4. Fill in the rule information based on the rule type selected:
 - For Threshold rules:
 - Which event type to monitor?: Select the event type that the rule will monitor (e.g. Failed Login)
 - Alert when count reaches: Set the threshold for the rule (e.g. 5)
 - Within a time window of: Set the time window for the rule (e.g. 1 minute)
 - Group by (optional): Select to group by IP address or user. This will group results by the selected field.
 - For Sequence rules:
 - First event type: Select the first event type to monitor (e.g. Failed Login)
 - Then event type: Select the second event type to monitor (e.g. Successful Login)
 - Within how long? Set the time window for the sequence to occur (e.g. 5 minutes)
 - Match by: Select to match by IP address or user. This requires the events to be from the same IP or user for the rule to be matched.
 - For Threshold-Sequence rules:
 - First event type: Select the first event type to monitor (e.g. Failed Login)
 - Alert when this event occurs at least: Set the threshold for the first event (e.g. 50)
 - Then followed by event type: Select the second event type to monitor (e.g. Successful Login)
 - Within a time window of: Set the time window for the sequence to occur (e.g. 10 minutes)
5. Check the information provided and click “Create Rule” to add the rule to the database. The new rule will be enabled by default and applied to all future scans. To apply the new rule to historic scans, reprocess them from the dashboard.

Figure 32: Annotated screenshot of new rule information being added

F.3 Running Tests

21 unit tests have been developed to check core functionality delivers expected behaviour.

Unit tests can be run by executing the following command from the project directory:

```
pytest
```

F.4 Generating Logs

To run the log generation script, from the project root execute:

```
python -u log_generator.py
```

The script will generate the following files for each size (100k, 250k, 500k, 1m), which are stored in 'datasets/'

- `baseline_<size>.log`
 - Baseline log containing normal activity
 - `baseline_<size>_ground_truth.csv`
 - Ground truth for the baseline log, showing for each event whether it is normal or malicious (all are normal for the baseline file).
 - `bruteforce_<size>.log`
 - Log containing a brute force attack, in addition to normal activity ('noise').
 - `bruteforce_<size>_ground_truth.csv`
 - Ground truth for the brute force log, showing for each event whether it was performed as part of an attack or normal activity (noise).
 - `bruteforce_<size>_attacks.json`
 - JSON file containing the details of each attack, including how many malicious and normal events were performed, and whether the attack concluded with a login success or not.
-

F.5 Troubleshooting / FAQs

How do I run the application?

1. Ensure you have Python 3.8+ and pip.
2. Install dependencies with `pip install -r requirements.txt`.
3. Run the app with `streamlit run gui.py`.
4. Access the dashboard at `http://localhost:8501` in your web browser.

Is there anything else I need to set up?

No. The database automatically initialises on the first run, and default rules are added if no rules exist.

What file formats can I upload?

Currently, only SSH authentication logs (e.g. `/var/log/auth.log`) are supported.

What events are extracted from the logs?

The following events are extracted:

- Failed Login (incorrect password)
- Failed Login (invalid user)
- Successful Login

My file had no events extracted, why?

This could be due to a few reasons:

- The file does not contain any SSH authentication events
- The file format is not a standard auth.log format
- Timestamps in the file are in an unexpected format

The file I analysed returned no alerts, why?

This could be due to a few reasons:

- No enabled rule was matched
- Rule thresholds may be too high/strict
- The scan doesn't contain enough malicious activity

I changed a rule, but it hasn't updated the results for my past scans, why?

Rule changes are only applied to new scans. To re-run a scan using new rules, select it on the dashboard and click `View detailed results`.

Where is my data stored?

Scan metadata and rules are stored within `data/app.db`, using SQLite. Event data is stored in `data/scans/<scan_id>.duckdb`, using DuckDB.

Can I recover a deleted scan?

Once a scan is deleted, it is permanently removed from the database and cannot be recovered.

G Unit Testing

test_db.py

- Test that initialising the database creates the necessary tables and default rules
- Test that inserting a scan and its events works correctly and that it can be retrieved
- Test that updating the alert counts for a scan edits the values in the database
- Test CRUD operations for rules

test_log_parser.py

- Test a failed password event is parsed correctly
- Test a successful login event is parsed correctly
- Test that irrelevant lines are ignored
- Test that an empty file returns an empty dataframe with mandatory columns

test_processing.py

- Test that common alias columns are correctly mapped to canonical names
- Test that standardising the dataframe drops invalid data
- Test that standardising the dataframe adds NaN values for missing columns
- Test that standardising an empty dataframe still generates canonical columns

test_results.py

- Test `activity_series` to check an empty input returns an empty dataframe with events column
- Test `activity_series` creates a time series with the correct number of events for each timestamp
- Test `activity_series` uses 5 min buckets when the timespan is 1 day
- Test `activity_series` uses hourly buckets when the timespan is over 60 days

test_rules_engine.py

- Test threshold rule triggers when expected
- Test sequence rule triggers when expected
- Test threshold-sequence rule triggers when expected
- Test that `execute_rule` can handle a JSON rule config
- Test that all rules execute even if one causes an error

```
(.venv) PS C:\Users\harry\PycharmProjects\FinalProject> pytest -q --
  disable-warnings
..... [100%]
21 passed, 1 warning in 1.57s
```

A sample of the unit tests are included below. All tests can be found within the tests directory of the project root.

```
from io import BytesIO
from core.log_parser import parse_auth_log

# Test a failed password event is parsed correctly
def test_parse_failed_password_event():
    # Create a line representing a failed login
    line = b"Mar  1 10:23:45 host sshd[1234]: Failed password for
           user1 from 192.168.1.100\n"

    df = parse_auth_log(BytesIO(line))

    assert len(df) == 1 # Check only one event is created
    assert df.iloc[0]["event"] == "login_fail" # Check it has been
        correctly classified as a failed login
    assert df.iloc[0]["user"] == "user1" # Check the username is
        extracted correctly

# Test that irrelevant lines are ignored
def test_parse_mixed_lines_ignores_non_sshd():
    # Create 3 lines, 2 'noise' and 1 invalid user
    content = b"""Mar  1 10:00:00 host kernel: unrelated
Mar  1 10:00:01 host sshd[11]: Invalid user ghost from 8.8.8.8
Mar  1 10:00:02 host sudo: another unrelated
"""

    df = parse_auth_log(BytesIO(content))

    assert len(df) == 1 # Check only 1 event is created (2 dropped)
    assert df.iloc[0]["event"] == "invalid_user" # Check the parsed
        event is invalid user
    assert df.iloc[0]["user"] == "ghost" # Check the username is
        extracted correctly
```